

Periodic Report 1

EU Grants: Periodic Report (V1.1 – 01.05.2023)

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Report overview

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1	10.03.2024	Initial draft merging all WP reports
2	12.03.2024	Restructuring of chapters
3	22.03.2024	Offline editing of the report
4	28.03.2024	Final review by project partners
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Executive summary

The DIRECTED Project was awarded an Innovation Action Grant by the Horizon Europe Programme in October 2022. This report sees the first of three periodic reviews set as a part of the ongoing development and implementation of the DIRECTED Project. The report summarises comprehensive work that has been ongoing between the period of October 2022 to the 31st of December 2023 and therefore represents the initial phase of the four-year project.

The first fifteen months has primarily included:

- The set-up and understanding of issues, data and tool availability that is seen at grassroots levels within the four Real World Labs – in The Capital Region of Copenhagen, Emilia-Romagna, Rhine-Erft and Danube Regions. This has included building stakeholder partnerships at local level.
- The understanding of data standards required for the work on the interoperability of tools and services offered by partners and how these tools can be made interoperable for the benefit of the Real World Labs
- Initial augmentation and further development of existent models, tools and methods towards main-streaming, enhanced interoperability and applicability within the Real World Labs and beyond (aligned with above-mentioned points)
- The integration of Tandem co-production and co-design of tools with a range of risk governance systems in the Risk-Tandem Framework was completed.
- Application of the Risk-Tandem Framework in the four Real World Labs has begun and will continue in an iterative process to understand current and future risk governance challenges
- Initial analyses were carried out to understand data availability at Real World Lab and Project level and how these tools and governance systems may be improved using the Data Fabric
- Set-up of all communications and dissemination channels and project branding and first phase work in this in line with our communications and dissemination strategy
- Reaching out to and knowledge exchanges with related projects and initiatives within the sphere of DIRECTED
- Set-up of all project agreements and management systems, as well as baseline planning on data management and ethics.

The report summarises work under each of the eight Work Packages and provides updates on each of the tasks as outlined in the grant agreement and as well as updates on deliverables, milestones, objectives, and impacts. The report also highlights deviations to the original DIRECTED Project plans.

Collaboration between all consortium partners has been strong throughout the entire first reporting period with high participation and engagement in project meetings and activities (see Annex 1). The combined effort has led to the completion off the majority of planned deliverables, milestones and tasks in this reporting period.

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List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
API	APPLICATION PROGRAMMING INTERFACE
CCA	CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION
CDS	COPERNICUS CLIMATE DATA STORE
DMP	DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN
DRM	DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT
DRR	DISASTER RISK REDUCTION
EFAS	EUROPEAN FLOOD AWARENESS SYSTEMS
FAIR	FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSABLE
FPC	FLOOD PROTECTION CORPORATION
GA	GENERAL ASSEMBLY
GloFAS	GLOBAL FLOOD AWARENESS SYSTEMS
ICPDR	INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION FOR THE PROTECTION OF THE DANUBE RIVER
OKF	NATIONAL DIRECTORATE GENERAL FOR DISASTER MANAGEMENT
OGC	OPEN GEOSPATIAL CONSORTIUM
PSC	PROJECT STEERING COMMITTEE
RWL	REAL WORLD LAB
SDG	SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS
WP	WORK PACKAGE

1 Overview and Progress

The recent droughts and unprecedented floods in 2021 and 2023 in Europe have illustrated our vulnerability to extreme weather events. Besides climate change as a driver of more frequent and intensifying weather extremes, demographic change and socio-economic development exacerbate severe impacts. International frameworks for Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation (e.g. SENDAI framework, EU Climate Adaptation Strategy & EU Disaster Risk Management policies) acknowledge the critical need for integrating risk governance, communication and operational mechanisms for coping with extreme climate. DIRECTED seeks to foster disaster-resilient societies through improving collaborations and communication among scientific, technical, and policy-makers, and local communities regarding extreme climate events and a multi-risk perspective on forest fires, droughts, floods, heat-waves, and storms, to support Disaster Risk Reduction. Our four European Real World Labs (RWL's) are at the centre of our efforts to improve interoperability for data, models, communication and governance in the context for Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA). DIRECTED will improve interoperability with an integrated federated system, which connects different instances and data sources on public and private clouds under a centralized interface, known as a Data Fabric. The Data Fabric will adapt to changing CCA and DRM requirements for data, models and visualizations. Our RWLs will co-produce a plug and play system that lowers the cost of implementing new and connecting existing modelling environments and data sources.

DIRECTED has seven core objectives, which include creating an overview of current knowledge, policies, tools, and best practices for DRM and CCA decision-making; advancing the interoperability of data, models, and tools; co-developing a new multi-level integrated risk governance framework (Risk-Tandem Framework) for the coherent integration between DRM and CCA policies; demonstrating the potential of transdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder co-production as a means to unpack enablers, barriers for developing transformative tools and improved risk management strategies; leveraging innovative digital architectures using a Data Fabric technique to support integrated multi-hazard DRM and CCA workflows; demonstrating the feasibility for integrated cross-sectoral and transdisciplinary coordination of the DRM cycle; and strengthening DRM and resilience-building in our RWLs and beyond.

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1.1 Objectives

The Table below tracks project objectives as they are described in the DoA. It provides a short summary of our progress on the pathway towards these objectives.

Table 1: Progress on project objectives.

Objective	Progress Pathway
(SO1) Create an overview of current knowledge, policies, tools, best practices and key actors, their interoperability, and how they influence decisions on DRR and CCA	<p>Initial assessment of tools and data sources used in the RWLs has been carried out. Tools and best practice examples have been demonstrated by partners to the consortium during in a series of talks during bi-weekly “Jour Fixe” meetings.</p> <p>For the creation of the Risk-Tandem Framework, WP 3 and 4 have all worked with state-of-the-art scholarship from their respective research fields. Further, a desktop review has been undertaken to better understand the relevant stakeholders in the respective RWLs, their role in the decision-making process. Fully illuminating the decision-process alongside the existing norms and policies within the varying RWLs will be a central research question for Task 3.2 and beyond.</p>
(SO2) Advance the interoperability of data, models and tools	<p>There has been an update of the CaMa-Flood version in the Danube Model and an increase of the spatial resolution; this required a shift from irregular subbasins to grid-based data. SaferPlaces OGC API Proof of Concept has been developed.</p> <p>Co-development meetings for the design of the Data Fabric were held with the modelling teams and RWL partners.</p>
(SO3) Co-develop a new multi-level integrated risk governance framework for the coherent integration between DRR and CCA policies and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).	<p>Development of the Risk-Tandem Framework (Deliverable 3.1, submitted January 2024)</p> <p>Through the development of the Risk-Tandem Framework, the existing DRR and CCA policies employed throughout the RWLs are also being assessed with regards to their justice and sustainability claims. In this sense, the application of the framework and the subsequent iterative evolution process will also yield results for synergistic effects of region specific DRR and CCA, and the SDGs more broadly.</p> <p>Implementation of Risk-Tandem Framework (Deliverable 3.2, Work in Progress)</p>
(SO4) Demonstrate the potential of transdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder co-production as a means to unpack enablers	<p>The potential of transdisciplinary co-production was demonstrated in “World Cafe” sessions with RWL partners, modelers and governance</p>

<p>and barriers for developing transformative tools and improved risk management strategies.</p>	<p>experts during the GA in Cologne.</p>
<p>(SO5) Leverage innovative digital architectures using Data Fabric technique to support integrated multi-hazard DRR and CCA workflows.</p>	<p>Requirements have been collected and first high-level designs have been sketched and discussed</p>
<p>(SO6) Demonstrate the feasibility for integrated cross-sectoral and transdisciplinary coordination of the DRM cycle (from prevention, preparedness, to response, and recovery) in the framework of real-life case scenarios based on interoperable tools (SO2) and multi-level risk governance frameworks (SO3).</p>	<p>The SaferPlaces system was used under a real-life disaster situation by the Emilia-Romagna Civil Protection organisation in May 2023.</p>
<p>(SO7) Strengthen DRR and resilience-building in the RWLs (and beyond)</p>	<p>First impact has been achieved through raising awareness of existing tools and initiating communication among stakeholders in the RWLs.</p>

1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per WP

The progress of work in the project is presented in the following sections. Each work package presents an overview of their progress on deliverables, milestones and tasks in a table format with a brief status report based on the DIRECTED Grant Agreement, Annex I. More details are given in narrative form per task with a reference to the project partners that have lead the tasks and contributed to the work. We also report on all the deliverables, milestones and tasks finalized in this reporting period and on tasks where work has commenced during the first 16 months of the project, but has not yet been completed.

1.2.1 Work Package 1 – Real World Labs

Initiating Real World Labs (RWLs) has been the main goal of Work Package 1 for this reporting period. This has involved engaging stakeholders, starting the co-production of knowledge process, and setting up governance mechanisms within the Risk-Tandem Framework. Specific objectives of the period have been achieved as testified by the Deliverable D1.1. Detailing RWL setup, and D1.2. Guidance on implementing transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes in the RWL based on the Tandem Framework, outlining a training strategy for stakeholders, produced by SEI. Furthermore, preparatory work on Evaluation and Outcomes/ Impact monitoring of the RWL (led by RIFS) started as planned. Contributions to the WP 1 activities involved, task leaders, co-leaders and all partners and in particular RWL responsible partners, to manage the Labs and interact with other WPs. Despite some deviation from the original plans (outlined in Section 5), the work has been pivotal for fostering effective operations and stakeholder participation in RWLs, as described in detail in the following chapters.

1.2.1.1 Introduction

Work Package 1 (WP 1) focuses on establishing and then managing the Real World Labs (RWL), to foster collaborative learning and innovation by engaging key stakeholders in the Disaster Risk Management (DRM), Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR), and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) cycle. Through tasks aimed at setting up, operating, and evaluating these labs, WP1 emphasizes knowledge co-production and stakeholder involvement to facilitate implementation of multi-level risk governance. The activities span from initial setup and stakeholder engagement to implementing co-production processes and evaluating outcomes, aiming to enhance governance mechanisms and promote effective multi-stakeholder engagement within the Risk-Tandem Framework.

1.2.1.2 Progress per task

Table 2: Summary of deliverables, milestones, and tasks status in WP 1.

Deliverables, Milestones and Tasks	Status report
D1.1 RWL description and set-up – (Lead Beneficiary: GECCO) Task 1.1	Status: D1.1 Submitted – Milestone 1, 2, 3 completed Task 1.1. Full set-up requirements of RWL's in Capital Region, Copenhagen, Emilia-Romagna and Rhine-Erft and the Danube Region completed.

Milestone 1,2	M3 discusses knowledge co-production outcomes based on the progress of Real World Labs.
D1.2 Capacity development strategy for Training of Trainers on implementing transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes in the RWL (Lead Beneficiary: SEI) Task 1.2	Status: D1.2 Submitted Task 1.2. Developed the operationalisation of the Risk-Tandem Framework.
D1.3 Case studies of DRR/ CCA processes to date - forensic examination of real-world process and events management (Lead Beneficiary: Oasis) Task 1.3	Status: Ongoing – due 30 Sep 2024 Initial meetings and information and data collection has begun for the Emilia-Romagna and Rhine-Erft comparative case study.
D1.4 Outcomes from RWL in multi-risk governance (Lead Beneficiary: GfZ) Task 1.3 Milestone 7	Status: - Not started – due 30 June 2026

Task 1.1 Setting up and making operational the Real World Laboratories (RWL) (M1-M10) (lead: GECO, co-lead: G&C, contributors: ALL)

This task effectively initiated and operationalized Real World Labs (RWLs) across diverse regions, addressing unique challenges in Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA).

Deliverable 1.1, "RWL Description and Setup" marks the completion of the task activities and acts as the first Periodic report on outcomes of the RWL co-production process and highlights the importance of engaging a broad spectrum of stakeholders, through a bottom-up approach, crucial for customizing RWLs to meet the specific needs and challenges of the different regions. This engagement was achieved through both formal and informal agreements and was later underscored by collecting letters of engagement. This has met the interim goal of Milestone 2. This foundational phase has involved framing the Stakeholders involved in each Lab (Milestone 1), mapping out disaster management frameworks and assessing climate change preparedness in different regions, including the Capital Region of Denmark, Emilia-Romagna in Italy, the Danube Region (covering Vienna, Austria; Budapest and Zala County, Hungary), and Germany's Rhine-Erft Region.

By prioritizing adaptive, region-specific strategies for stakeholder engagement and establishing robust communication channels (notably through online tools and boards for sharing and monitoring progress across Labs), this foundational phase has effectively set the stage for the subsequent implementation of the Risk-Tandem Framework and knowledge co-production processes, aligning closely with the project's aims of fostering integrated risk governance and encouraging transdisciplinary collaboration.

M3, the first periodic report on outcomes of the RWL knowledge co-production process discusses knowledge co-production outcomes based on the progress of Real World Labs in this period. Initially, this report was integrated into the D1.1. due to their similar aims, but is now

revised as a standalone document to further support Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (MEL) for knowledge co-production, as discussed in detail under D1.2. (The Capacity Development Strategy for DIRECTED). The document outlines achievements and progress to further complement D1.1. from the perspective of knowledge co-production, with an added focus on identified priorities, needs and challenges affecting collaborative working. This information will be used to guide and inform the development of capacity development modules to match training activities with contextual needs (alongside capacity needs assessments and individual consultations).

Figure 1: DIRECTED Real World Labs. RWL 1: Capital Region of Denmark, RWL 2: Emilia-Romagna Region, RWL 3: Danube Region, RWL 4: Rhine-Erft Region.

Task 1.2 RWL co-production process (M1-M45) (lead: SEI, co-lead: UCC, contributors: 52N, RWL partners)

Working with WPs 1 and 3, WP 4 has begun implementing the knowledge co-production process through Training of Trainers (as described in D1.2), complimenting the Risk-Tandem Framework (D3.1). First a capacity development module seeking to support the co-exploration of risks – and to introduce the contributions of WP 3/ WP 4 to DIRECTED – was delivered in June 2023. Tools introduced in this training were later utilized by RWL2 in their workshop dedicated to scoping, and similar exercises were also introduced in the General Assembly held in Cologne, September 2023 (to support RWLs in their planning, but also to improve the DIRECTED partners’ understanding of the working context). Besides these activities, WP 4 and WP 3 have continuously engaged with the RWLs via meetings, for instance to support RWL workshop design and delivery. They have also provided practical guidance on designing interviews and focus group discussions, as well as seeking to enable transdisciplinary stakeholder engagement by taking part in the process of setting up of RWLs. Now, following the first scoping consultations (M19), WP 4 continues capacity development on facilitating co-production via co-designed modules (D4.1), webinars, and other activities in alignment with the Risk-Tandem process with WP 3 (thus overcoming delays faced in setting up the RWLs in 2023).

With the support of Deliverables 1.2. and 3.1 (capacity development and the on-going application of the Risk-Tandem process) partners involved in WP 1 continue knowledge exchange and the development of strategies to enable and demonstrate **tangible improvements** in risk governance relating to DRR, CCA and systemic risk management in the RWLs. In other words, the transdisciplinary collaboration between DIRECTED partners, RWL hosts, and their stakeholders have begun developing knowledge and progress toward **scalable solutions** with

measurable impacts in real world settings – thus cultivating an evidence base for novel approaches. On the other hand, by working with partners from WP 5, WP 1 continues to increase the **practical applicability** and usability of state-of-the-art climate and risk data and models by providing inputs to the design of the Data Fabric (see Box 1). The RWLs, acting as **collaborative spaces** for learning and innovation, have seen a significant increase in their output and contributions towards achieving the ambitious outcomes outlined in the DIRECTED project's grant agreement. In the Labs we extensively use cutting-edge digital tools and platforms that facilitate continuous and interactive stakeholder engagement, coupled with traditional workshops and interviews.

The **integrated participatory approach**, followed in the laboratories from their setup phase, not only pushes the envelope in multi-hazard risk assessment but also in the practical application of these assessments to improve resilience and inform policy and practice in real-world contexts. Finally, recognizing the **critical role of local governance**, our participatory approach to the Lab activities not only involves stakeholders in the decision-making process but also in the co-design and co-implementation of solutions, thereby ensuring that strategies are more adaptable and tailored to specific local needs and in the longer term enable usability in the exploitation of developed processes and systems.

Ongoing Task 1.2 (as 1.3) is closely interlinked with WPs 3 and 4, focusing on applying the Risk-Tandem Framework (D3.1) supported by the strategy for capacity development for the training of trainers (D1.2). To achieve outcomes regarding increasing resilience through governance, communication, and information interoperability, partners continue this work in 2024 by applying the remaining Risk-Tandem tasks and risk management approaches (from co-exploring risk governance contexts to understanding capacity development needs, and most importantly, co-designing scalable and fit-for-purpose solutions based on this evidence). This process will be reported in the incoming Periodic reports on outcomes of the RWL co-production process #2 under preparation in Task 1.2 as ongoing active Milestone 8 and will be aided by WP 4 by continuing scope of RWL needs and by designing capacity development interventions, aims to maximize the potential of RWLs in terms of enabling transdisciplinary knowledge co-production (applied through autonomous RWL workshops).

D1.2 Capacity development strategy for Training of Trainers on implementing transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes in the RWL (SEI)

The main ambition of this strategy is to empower Trainers to pursue DIRECTED's ambitions in their Real-World Lab's through co-exploration of issues and co-production of solutions relating to holistic risk management, governance strategies and data interoperability issues with local stakeholders. The strategy outlines an approach to enabling these through capacity development, beginning with a discussion regarding the theoretical and contextual challenges of multi-hazard risk governance in the European context, as well as integrating different DRM and CCA knowledges, data, or disciplines towards holistic risk reduction with the support of knowledge co-production. This approach enables locally led and tailored implementation of DIRECTED based on priorities identified by stakeholders themselves, reflecting the unique needs of stakeholders in the RWLs.

Task 1.3 Evaluation and Outcomes/Impact monitoring of the RWL (M8-M48) (lead: RIFS, co-lead: G&C, contributors: OASIS, UCC, IIASA, RWL partners)

This task focuses on evaluating the Risk-Tandem Framework within the RWLs, assessing its effectiveness in enhancing multi-stakeholder engagement, improving interoperability, and facilitating knowledge exchange for DRR and CCA integration. Despite not marking so far any expected official milestones or deliverables, the initial steps taken involved understanding each RWL's specific data, governance, and communication challenges through guidance documents and stakeholder workshop questionnaires, in collaboration with Work Packages 3 and 4. Based on the results of workshops, desk research and a serious game conducted at the GA in Cologne in September 2023 and continuous exchange with the RWLs, an initial scoping

of the governance context as well as governance needs has been conducted. Progressing towards assessing Risk-Tandem's impact, development of a methodology using both quantitative and qualitative indicators has started and D1.3 Case Study (due next September 2024) has been planned.

D1.3 Case Study (due next September 2024). The case study from this task has been planned and initiated, and it will focus on comparing July 2021 floods in Rhine-Erft and May 2023 floods in Emilia-Romagna, to offer a detailed analysis for enhancing future disaster management. This comparison will highlight lessons learned, successes, and areas for improvement from these major flood events and to define the report's scope, leveraging existing reports, papers, and communications on these significant flood events and collection of relevant material such as reports, papers, and communications related these events has been already started.

Joint activities with WPs 3 and 4 include, active milestones include M12. (WP 3/4 milestone on engaging with the RWLs in a co-productive mode), M19 (scoping consultations), progress toward D4.1 (capacity development modules for ToT workshops), and tasks/milestones associated with the iterative refinement of the Risk-Tandem and Tandem Frameworks based on emerging evidence (T3.3/T4.4).

Preparation work that is adjusting the hazard risk models to be used within the Real World Labs is also underway. The Danube Model had been originally developed at PIK as “Future Danube Model” in the EU INSURANCE project which ended in 2020. Both its components, the eco-hydrological model SWIM, used here for simulating runoff generation, and the hydrodynamical flood model CaMa-Flood have seen further development since, and many input and validation data have reached higher coverage, resolution, and quality in the meantime. To maintain the Danube Model at the current technological standard, recent E-OBS weather data were applied at 0.1-degree resolution (formerly 0.25 degrees) for re-calibration. Moreover, the CaMa-Flood part was swapped entirely for the most recent model version (4.1). This advanced the internal and output spatial representation from irregularly shaped subbasins to grids of higher resolution, namely 0.05 degrees (approx. 5 km). Figure 16 shows an example runoff output for a single day. A near-real-time application has been tested for the flood in Slovenia on 4th August 2023 and the following days, a first step towards an operative forecasting application dubbed “Seamless Forecasting Tool”. With a special stack of raster layers derived from MERIT and obtained directly from the leader of the CaMa-Flood development group Dai Yamazaki (University Tokyo) it is now possible to make very high resolution (approx. 90 m) downscaling products for single events.

Also, GFZ tested and will further develop usage of its hydrodynamic model, RIM2D, to set-up a flood inundation model for the Erft Region which will enable the production of flood maps for the area. An initial simulation run of the model is depicted in Figure 24.

Figure 2: Gridded runoff in the Danube River Basin, example of a daily output from the Danube Model developed at PIK.

Figure 3: Initial flood simulation results from RIM2D (hydrodynamic model by GFZ) for the Erft Region.

1.2.1.3 Stakeholder engagement

Below, we offer an update on stakeholder engagement from October 2023 to January 2024, supplementing the information previously documented in D1.1 "RWL Description and Setup". As noted in the deviations section 5.1.1 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**, we encountered some delays, but have adjusted the plans for interaction to address and mitigate any setbacks or slowdown faced, ensuring project objectives remain on track. Further details on these adjustments and the organization carried on for upcoming stakeholder engagements will be outlined.

RWL 1: The Capital Region of Denmark

Interviews

The RWL 1 conducted a series of interviews with stakeholders back in the spring of 2023. The aim was to get a closer understanding of what challenges the stakeholders face regarding data use and sharing, organisation and collaboration and finally communication during climate related events but also regarding dialogue between Disaster Risk Management and stakeholders in charge of climate adaptation. To further comprehend the challenges and to better understand where DIRECTED might be able to make a difference for the way response and adaptation is conducted and not least potentially be intertwined, a second round of interviews has been prepared. To that end RWL 1 has formulated an interview guide to ensure a standard output across the three interview sessions planned. The interviews were held in March/April 2024.

The sum of identified challenges from the interview sessions is as follows:

Data and Modelling Needs:

1. Emergency agencies rely on data from the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI). There is a demand for more accurate forecasts given the high cost of mobilizing and deploying emergency resources. Specifically, the emergency services point towards a tendency to overestimate sea levels during events, which leads to unnecessary and costly measures in certain areas.
2. There is a desire for better models to assess the consequences of coupled events (high water levels in the Roskilde fjord in combination with heavy rainfall and increased river discharge). In this scenario, the duration of the high-water levels in the fjord becomes important, as well as the capacity of pumps to pump water from the river to the fjord in areas where coastal defense mechanisms such as sluice gates are in place. Additionally, there is a desire for wave height to be incorporated into warning systems.
3. Free models (Klimaatlas, GEUS nationale hydrologiske model) and private consultant mapping solutions like SCALGO are available to municipalities. More detailed and accurate models provided by consulting firms are generally more expensive, and thus not always used in climate adaptation plans. Collaboration with utility companies can be an option for municipalities to access more advanced models and data.
4. An accessible overview of climate tools and models, with a description of what they can do, where the data can be accessed, and from which source the data is retrieved from, would also be beneficial.
5. There is a desire among municipalities for additional local measuring points and weather stations to supply forecast information as an event unfolds. A common system enabling real-time data sharing across municipalities could be beneficial.

6. Not all the municipalities have designated GIS (Geographic Information System) employees. Some emergency agencies require pro-active maps sharing from municipalities.
7. Klimaatlas offers climate projections based on a low emissions scenario (RCP 2,6), a medium-high emissions scenario (RCP 4,5) and a high emissions scenario (RCP 8,5). It is not always clear which climate change scenario and time horizon should be considered for climate adaptation. There can be differences among municipalities.

Organizational Needs:

1. Differing warning levels/systems among municipalities covered by the same emergency agency offer some potential for standardization.
2. Currently there's no systematic coordination or communication mechanism in place between municipalities when formulating their emergency plans. Considering that storm surge and water course flooding impacts extend beyond administrative boundaries, it could make sense to promote dialogue and coordination among neighboring municipalities.
3. Roskilde fjord is covered by two police districts (Nordsjællands Politi og Midt-og Vestsjællands Politi), emphasizing the coordination needs during a storm surge event impacting the whole fjord. In each of the country's 12 police districts, a local emergency response team (LBS) has been established under the leadership of the chief of police to coordinate emergency preparedness tasks. The police assume thus, the coordinating leadership when several authorities are involved in specific emergency response operations. To strengthen coordination between defense, police and other civilian authorities in the event of major crises in Denmark a national operational staff (NOST) was established in 2005. At the municipal level, it's not always clear how coordination mechanisms across municipalities operate. A simulation event could be a useful preparedness exercise, which could be coordinated under the DIRECTED efforts, if an interest among the Real-World Lab stakeholders exists. A preparedness exercise could help also mapping the resources required for such a simulation.
4. There can be to some extent a challenge when incidents occur on weekends and holidays when municipal employees may not be available. Some emergency agencies require pro-active information (updated contact lists, maps) sharing from municipalities during an emergency.
5. Some municipalities hope for new legislation addressing the distribution of protection responsibilities in vulnerable coastal areas highly exposed to storm surges.
6. To different extents municipalities carry out an evaluation after an emergency. There may be potential to develop a more systematic evaluation system among the actors involved in the recovery phase. Systematic data collection and analysis during the recovery phase can help guide future climate adaptation efforts.
7. A good dialogue between municipalities and emergency agencies is crucial. New climate adaptation interventions must be reported to the emergency services and reflected into emergency plans. Additionally, the experience on the ground from the emergency services should be capitalized in the municipality's climate adaptation

plans. Citizen involvement can also be used to gather experience and knowledge to guide climate adaptation measures at the municipal level.

Communication Needs:

1. Since Bodil (2013) there have been training programs addressed to citizens on how to prepare themselves for the impacts of a storm (i.e., how to use sandbags to protect their homes). Additionally in June 2024, a water management center opened in the Roskilde Fire Department to test new solutions and offer training to emergency services and volunteers.
2. Communication with citizens and adequately managing citizens' expectations during an emergency are crucial. It is important to ensure citizens understand their own responsibility during a storm as well as how they can best protect themselves, their properties, and assist their neighbors. In this sense, some municipalities believe they can strengthen their current communication systems and citizen guidance materials.
3. Municipalities could benefit from sharing good practices when elaborating communication materials addressed to citizens. Some emergency agencies have also valuable communication experience.
4. A common communication platform could be useful to gather information during emergencies impacting the whole fjord, alternatively, current communication systems and coordination could be strengthened to make sure everyone has access to the same knowledge and information at the same time.
5. Emergency agencies have a good cooperation but there might be opportunities to strengthen communication and dialogue during emergencies. This would require cooperation with the police districts.

Other remarks:

1. Events and collective memory are essential regarding the amount of attention towards Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) and Disaster Risk Management (DRM). It has been over ten years since the storm Bodil (2013), and hence people are starting to forget its impacts. Overall, there should be more political awareness and attention on Climate Change Adaptation and Disaster Risk Management.
2. There is a lack of focus on retreat as a climate adaptation strategy. The focus is currently set on protective hard and mobile measures. An increase in the frequency and intensity of storms might however require alternative climate adaptation approaches.
3. Given the goal of Danish emergency services to reduce the use of clean water by at least 50% by 2030 it could be relevant to explore synergies with municipal climate adaptation plans. A possibility could be to consider whether there are potential locations for collecting rainfall surface water in reservoirs to be used by emergency agencies during, for example firefighting efforts.
4. Political priorities and economical restraints on both Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation are seen as factors restraining both municipalities and emergency services from addressing some of the needs described above.

Workshops

The outcome of the interviews will be used as basis for a series of workshops held with stakeholders with the first planned to be held on August the 20th 2024. To the local stakeholders the reference point for DRM and CCA in the Roskilde Fjord is the 2013 storm surge known as 'Bodil' in Denmark. For that reason, the workshop will be centred on the discussion of whether or not the area is prepared for a Bodil version 2.0. Meaning that DIRECTED at will present modelling of how a similar storm surge with the added climate change factors might play out in 2050. Together with the presentation of a mapping of the identified challenges to the stakeholders and outline how the project can help rectify these, the aim is to get a clearer picture of in what way a more direct collaboration between project and stakeholders can help solve specific needs in the Roskilde Fjord area. Through dialogue about the identified organisational challenges and needs combined with a better understanding of how future climatic events might play out, the aim is to have the workshop conclude on which specific areas within DRM and CCM DIRECTED should focus its resources in order to assist the stakeholders.

RWL 2: The Emilia-Romagna Region

Workshops

The second workshop of the RWL 2 took place in Ferrara on 28 September 2023, it was organized by ARSTPC-ER and Geco sistema srl; ARPAE, was present as partners of the project, and the Municipalities of the test areas took part: Comacchio and Mesola (FE) for the risk of forest fires; Rimini and Riccione, on the Rimini coast, for coastal risk; the multi-services provider (Hera) and the Coordination of the voluntary civil protection associations of Ferrara and Rimini. Tshi and others Activities have been documented using Miro Board interactive tool (See) to access minutes, presentations and discuss outcomes inside WP 1 as done with other labs (full Miro accessible [here](#))

The activity in the morning focused on the discussion between the subjects involved on the following topics: territorial context, governance (actors) of the alert and emergency management processes, technical tools available and communication procedures in use. To optimize sharing between participants, the world café participation technique was used. The work of "Analysis of the governance process of the Disaster Risk Reduction - DDR - and Climate Change Adaption CCA" was carried out in two tables coordinated by the officials of the Regional Agency, one table on the risk of forest fires and table two on the coastal risk.

Webinars

A webinar was organised on the 20th of November 2023, with the Stakeholders previously involved in the second Workshop of Ferrara (28th September 2023). The webinar focused on data and tools for risk management and adaptation in the two pilots cases (Italian video record available [here](#)).

Meetings

ARSTPC-ER along with Gecosistema S.r.l. are organizing the Rimini event that will take place in Rimini in the date of 13-15 June 2024 during which there will be the General Assembly and a civil protection exercise with Stakeholders involved in the project.

Figure 4: Example of the interactive Miro Board used to collect ongoing progresses of RWLs including RWL 2 outcomes of September 2023 workshop.

RWL 3: Danube Region

Test site Vienna:

For efficiency reasons, communication has predominantly taken place through video calls and phone conversations since October 2023. Occasionally, on-site meetings were arranged for the dissemination of the project with the aim of stakeholder engagement and the exchange of relevant information (e.g., November 27-29, 2023, in Vienna with Generali, Uniqa, JRC) and presentations at events (e.g., DAFF Budapest, October 9-11, 2023). In November and December 2023, questionnaires tailored to each stakeholder group were prepared, and these were filled out and returned in January and February.

To facilitate the Stakeholder Workshop planned for May in Vienna, various stakeholders were contacted in January to ascertain preferences regarding the location and timing of the workshop. The BOKU Vienna has been identified as a more suitable venue than the training centre in Graz, although the exact date is yet to be confirmed.

In addition to engaging with external stakeholders, video calls were conducted with project partners from various work packages to prepare and organize the workshop.

Internal meetings were also held to finalize the design of the Interoperability and Taxonomy Survey. This has already been shared with the main stakeholder. The results are expected by the end of March 2024.

We are invited to the 45th meeting of the expert group on flood protection of the ICPDR (International Commission for the Protection of the Danube River) on April 23-24, 2024 to present

the current status of the DIRECTED Project, with a focus on the RWL Danube. We hope for a valuable professional exchange regarding flood protection in the Danube Region and the acquisition of further stakeholders for our test sites.

Test site Zala Region:

The Zala Special Rescue Association has initiated cooperation with the National Office of the National Directorate General for Disaster Management (OKF) in the framework of the DIRECTED Project in the areas related to the Project. Both the county organisation and the national Directorate General expressed their openness. Starting in October 2023, the representatives of both parties identified four areas of cooperation during the monthly regular meetings:

- Educational cooperation - the results, contacts and research findings of the DIRECTED Project could be used in the training of firefighters
- The preparation of a disaster risk map of one of the priority areas (TBD), West-Hungary, Zala county, or Budapest agglomeration, in the framework of the DIRECTED Project, using databases provided by the OKF
- Cooperation in applying new proposals and development projects
- Joint dissemination of DIRECTED Project results to the public and local communities, joint communication

The first concrete result of this cooperation was that the Directorate (OKF) invited project manager Levente Huszti on a study visit to Germany. They jointly visited the Würzburg Firefighter's School, one of the most modern German schools, where first responders, rescuers, and firefighters are trained.

On 21 February, a visit to the Bavarian Federal State Firefighter's School took place, where Michael Bräuer, the school director, Stephan Brust, deputy director, and Jürgen Schemmel, unit leader, received the Hungarian delegation. The heads of the school were personally available throughout the day; they explained the school's operations and activities and answered our questions in a very detailed and helpful manner.

The fire school itself is a training centre adjacent to the residential area of the city of Würzburg. As a stand-alone campus, it consists of several separate buildings in which a variety of exercises and damage simulations can be carried out (Fire Drill House, Incident Training Hall, Incident Training Area, First and Second Fire Station, VR Training Area, condominium, high-rise, railway situation area, gas station, workshop, fast food restaurant, farm buildings, lakeside, river flooding and underpass flooding with flash flood rescue simulations).

In the Federal State of Bavaria, there are 7,700 volunteer fire brigades with approximately 320,000 volunteer firefighters and, in addition, seven professional fire brigades in significant cities. The annual number of incidents is around 240,000 in the province, which is increasingly challenging for fire and emergency response and rescue organisations due to the extreme weather conditions caused by climate change. In the long term, climate change will alter the composition of vegetation cover, which in the short term, coupled with dry summers, will result in new and more destructive types of bush and forest fires. Specific curricula for these should be developed in training schools. Climate change is increasingly mentioned in training courses and is now part of the curriculum.

After the study trip, the Project Manager of ZKM and the leading experts of the OKF assessed that there is a need to launch a joint training programme in Zala County, in which professional and volunteer disaster managers and fire brigades can participate. The curriculum should respond to the challenges posed by climate change at the local (Zala County) level. The planned production of local and regional disaster risk maps in the DIRECTED Project could greatly help in this respect in the future. ZKM and OKF will continue the cooperation and request ZKM

to forward the request to the DIRECTED Partners with data requirements for the necessary risk mapping exercise.

RWL 4: Rhine-Erft Region

The Rhine-Erft Region RWL conducted three meetings with its stakeholders until the end of the first reporting period.

Meetings

The **first stakeholder meeting** was held online on 19th of April 2023. The aim was to introduce DIRECTED to the stakeholders, as well as to encourage a first exchange between them. After an initial discussion during this meeting, a questionnaire was sent out to the stakeholders to receive some answers on e.g. what their experiences were during the flood event in 2021 and if they have concrete ideas to improve Disaster Risk Management (DRM) in the region (for more details e.g. participants, see Deliverable 1.1).

The **second stakeholder meeting** took place on June 29, 2023, at the Erftverband building in Bergheim. Based on the stakeholder's answers to the questionnaire, a fruitful discussion developed, which led to first concrete issues that can be addressed in DIRECTED in RWL 4. Communication and support in the assessment of (hydrological) situations was emphasized (for more details e.g. attendees, see Deliverable 1.1).

The **third stakeholder meeting** was also held in-person at the Erftverband building on 20th of November 2023. It was used to deepen the exchange between the stakeholders and to offer them a platform to explain the issues they face in more detail. The discussion also addressed the targeted intersection between the Erftverband and the disaster management authorities and offered an initial idea for implementation. Further, the exchange between the stakeholders and employees of the Erftverband led to the idea of conducting a simulation exercise (table-top exercise) to better understand the processes during an extreme event.

There have also been project-internal meetings for exchange or support of RWL 4 (see **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**).

The idea of the simulation exercise will be concretized not only by research on the topic, but also through involvement of the stakeholders. A workshop section is planned for the next stakeholder meeting to develop an idea for carrying out such an exercise in RWL 4.

1.2.2 Work Package 2 – Interoperability

1.2.2.1 Introduction

Significant volumes of hazard and disaster-related data are presently accessible from a wide array of sources. However, these data are frequently scattered geographically, recorded in various formats, or under the ownership of different entities, rendering them challenging to access. The effectiveness of Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) relies on the capacity of multiple stakeholders to integrate, reuse, and distribute such disaster-related data. The primary objective of Work Package 2 within the DIRECTED project is to identify and gather a thorough range of standards designed to facilitate the exchange of data and information across various combinations of models, databases, and analytical/visualization tools. These standards are subsequently applied to existing tools and data to improve their functionalities and usability for Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) purposes. Key principles such as the FAIR data principles and other interoperable standards are carefully considered and utilized as the foundation for enhancing these tools. Additionally, within Work Package 2 of DIRECTED, selected models will demonstrate how data and knowledge from external tools or additional (open) data sources can be integrated into DRR and CCA workflows while ensuring interoperability along multiple dimensions.

1.2.2.2 Progress per task

Table 3: Summary of deliverables, milestones, and tasks status in WP 2.

Deliverables, Milestones and Tasks	Status report
D2.1 – Compendium on data standards for interoperability in DRR and CCA Milestone 8 Task 2.1	Status: In progress The collaborating partners are presently in the process of drafting an extensive report detailing the principles and criteria for interoperability, along with their corresponding evaluations. Due date: Month 24
D2.2 – Enhanced interoperability of tools available to users through software repository and documentation Milestone 9 Task 2.2	Status: In progress Work is in progress to enhance the interoperability of existing DRM tools and models (e.g. listed in the Grant Agreement) by integrating data and insights from various other key tools into their respective workflows. This is done in close collaboration with WP 5 to ensure compatibility with the Data Fabric. Due date: Month 36
D2.3 – Interoperability demonstration factsheets (description and illustration of workflow implementations in RWL as best practice examples) Task 2.3	Status: Planned This task involves evaluating alternative DRM and CCA strategies developed in the RWLs using the available models. Work on this deliverable has not yet begun. Due date: Month 48

Work Package 2 comprises three tasks along with their corresponding deliverables. An overview of the deliverables of each task and their status is depicted in the table provided above.

Task 2.1 Stocktaking for interoperability - a compendium (Month0-24) (lead: GECO, co-lead: 52N, contributors: GFZ, DTU, PIK, ETH, SEI, OASIS) is focused on establishing a framework for interoperable standards capable of exchanging data and information across various models, databases, and analytical and visualization tools. Within this task, participating partners are currently preparing a comprehensive report outlining the principles and standards for interoperability, along with their respective rankings. This report is evolving through continual collaboration and consultation among the various partners engaged in the Work Package, facilitated by regular online meetings and discussions. Additionally, an interoperability evaluation questionnaire is being developed for distribution among stakeholders in the Real World Labs (RWLs). The aim is to collect insights and feedback from stakeholders on subjects like taxonomy interoperability, data and tools interoperability, and open data and licensing. This input will inform how these topics can be effectively integrated into the subsequent tasks of the Work Package, ensuring they are precisely aligned with the needs of the stakeholders.

Currently, project members have contributed to this task as follows: GFZ has provided a report outlining principles and recommendations for interoperability, 52N has submitted a report on interoperable standards for data exchange, PIK has contributed a report on replicability and good practices, GECO has prepared a report ranking interoperable standards, and GECO has also led the preparation of an interoperability evaluation questionnaire for the RWLs, with its review being conducted by other project members. DTU is carrying out a formal literature review related to the propagation of information and uncertainties in impact modelling chains. The compilation is scheduled for submission in the 24th month of the project, in accordance with the planned timeline for September 2024. With regards to meetings, two were held in February 2023 and January 2024 concerning Task 2.1. These sessions delved into specific topics relevant to the task's main objectives. Additionally, for Task 2.1 a dedicated [Miro Board](#) has been generated with the purpose to share docs and collects suggestions and input from all the partners.

Figure 5: Chosen test location near Copenhagen, Denmark, used to validate the workflow of data exchange among the models and tools as an integral component of Task 2.1.

Task 2.2 Making tools interoperable (Month13-36) (lead: DTU, co-lead: ETH, contributors: PIK, GFZ, SEI, GECO, EV). Efforts are underway to refine available DRM tools and models to incorporate data and knowledge from other tools into their respective workflows, thereby enhancing their interoperability based on the findings from Task 2.1. The project members initiated work on Task 2.2 from the 13th month of the project (October 2023). Numerous meetings have been convened among project partners to establish a working plan and determine the most effective approach for executing the task. These meetings have involved comprehensive discussions and introductions of the project's models and tools. Essential input and output data, along with their formats, have been presented, and a workflow has been devised to seamlessly integrate each model with other tools, facilitating the exchange of data. To validate this workflow, an initial test area near Copenhagen, Denmark (Figure 32), has been selected by the project members, within the Capital Region of Copenhagen. Currently, all the necessary data required for setting up models for the chosen region using project tools is being compiled.

As part of Task 2.2, several enhancements have also been integrated into the existing models and tools to enhance their interoperability. For instance, a range of features has been incorporated into the hydrodynamic model RIM2D by GFZ. This includes the development of various tools as plugins for the open-source and free software QGIS, aimed at simplifying model setup and visualizing/processing results for RIM2D. These tools offer users an intuitive interface, making the utilization of RIM2D much more accessible. The interface of two of the developed tools is showcased in Figure 40, serving as exemplars. Moreover, the integration of these tools within QGIS expands the scope of acceptable file formats for use as inputs for RIM2D. This enhancement substantially boosts RIM2D's interoperability and aligns its compatibility with the various other tools utilized within the project. Moreover, additional functionalities have been added to RIM2D, such as the ability to utilize discharge timeseries for defining river boundary conditions within the model. RIM2D has also been enhanced to support the NetCDF file format, increasing its compatibility with other tools utilized in the project. These improvements collectively contribute to the ease of use and integration of RIM2D into the broader framework of tools and models utilized for the project's objectives.

Figure 6: Illustration of the user interfaces for the developed tools designed for the hydrodynamic model RIM2D as part of Task 2.1.

The SaferPlaces cloud web platform (Figure 48), has been made operational for RWL 2 Emilia-Romagna, stands ready to support extensive flood hazard mapping for pluvial and coastal scenarios, particularly in the Rimini Province area. The platform's capabilities are well-suited to bolster early warning systems, Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR), and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) efforts. To enhance SaferPlaces interoperability as part of Task 2.2, we've invested in technological advancements, integrating API technology into SaferPlaces. A preliminary design has been developed, aiming for Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) API services to be available by month 36 (Task 2.2). This will allow for seamless data exchange and integration with external systems, extending the platform's utility and reach. Both SaferPlaces by

GECOs and RIM2D by GFZ exemplify the cutting-edge in providing rapid flood risk intelligence, essential for Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA). Saferplaces excels in swiftly delivering comprehensive flood risk assessments, while RIM2D, a physically-based distributed hydrodynamic model, specializes in simulating pluvial, fluvial, and coastal floods. Leveraging GPUs, RIM2D achieves significantly reduced simulation times. Together, these models and services are invaluable for crafting advanced early warning systems, offering quick, accurate support for critical DRR and CCA initiatives.

Figure 7: Illustration of the user interface of the The SaferPlaces cloud web platform.

Moreover, as part of Task 2.2, work on the Danube Model hosted by PIK has been underway mainly focusing on the internal geo-spatial representation of sub-basins and river reaches – see WP 1. Further on, with regards to WP 2.2, necessary and optional data flows and output contents have been discussed between the partners, and the delivery of test data in operational formats was announced for the next reporting period.

Furthermore, among the tools in the project, CLIMADA, enables adaptation measure appraisals within its risk framework by conducting cost-benefit analyses, where the benefit is defined as the risk averted through various adaptation measures. The design of CLIMADA allows for risk modelling inputs, such as hazard, vulnerability, or exposure, to be sourced from other tools in the DIRECTED Project, underscoring interoperability. A new feature for Task 2.2 is the development of a Multi-Criteria module in CLIMADA, which can improve the adaptation measure appraisal by considering a variety of risk and cost metrics across multiple dimensions. Furthermore, this enhancement supports the integration of information from external sources into the decision-making process. It is specifically designed for allowing data to be added in a straightforward format (Pandas DataFrame) to the evaluation matrix. A prototype of this module has been developed and will undergo further refinement in the upcoming period.

Finally, the DamageCost Tool – a flexible high-resolution damage cost assessment tool developed for Denmark for carrying out multi-sectoral economic analyses related to the impact of pluvial, fluvial and coastal flood has been further refined. Using a new and optimized QGIS interface and through collaboration with stakeholders, the tool has during this reporting period been made seamlessly available to practitioners and municipalities, and emergency management agencies in Denmark through the national “OS2 digital collaboration”. Based on insights from e.g. CLIMADA and SaferPlaces, the tool is currently being ported and made available for a broader European audience. Insights from existing use will be ported to these tools. Pilot work, integrating damage cost curves from DamageCost into CLIMADA, is also ongoing.

With regards to meetings, for Task 2.2, two meetings took place in November and December 2023, involving key partners responsible for the task. During these meetings, the project's

models and tools were comprehensively introduced and reviewed, with discussions centred around their compatibility with other tools. Additionally, a comprehensive work plan was established and unanimously agreed upon for the task. Further meetings related to Work Package 2 and its tasks are scheduled for the future.

Task 2.3 Multi-hazard modelling for integrated DRM and CCA: Demonstration in RWLs (Month 24-48) (lead: GFZ, co-lead: PIK, SEI, contributors: DTU, GECO, EV, RIFS, UCC, G&C) is focused on evaluating and assessing alternative strategies of Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) developed in the RWLs using the models of the project. The results of this task will provide quantitative data to support discussions in the RWLs and aid in identifying comprehensive solutions. The work for this task is set to commence in month 24 of the project and falls outside of the reporting period.

1.2.3 Work Package 3 – Governance

1.2.3.1 Introduction

To improve governance interoperability, WP 3 will provide an innovative and empirically tested risk governance framework that facilitates the application of risk models to support DRR and CCA planning and decision-making processes and build long-term governance capacity for information and knowledge integration. Thus, the work carried out by WP 3 serves two overarching purposes. First, WP 3 contributes to the understanding and analysis of the existing governance structures, processes and actor constellations within the RWLs. This entails applying the Risk-Tandem Framework (Figure 56) to various practical situations, examining the structures, actor networks and constellations, formal and informal rules, modelling data, and other kinds of information that together form the baseline for the existing risk governance mechanisms. This work is mainly carried out in Task 3.1 and Task 3.2, i.e. the conceptual development phase of the Risk-Tandem Framework as well as its first application.

Figure 8: A schematic representation of the Risk-Tandem Framework.

Second, WP 3 works towards identifying and utilising governance leverage points within each RWL and in risk management settings for DRR and CCA more generally. Applying the Risk-

Tandem Framework in the RWLs will support identifying tailored governance mechanisms to guide and sustain the knowledge exchange between targeted users in the RWLs. Based on the conceptual and empirical work carried out in Tasks 3.1, 3.2, 3.3 and 1.3, the further development of the Risk-Tandem Framework through application, reflection, and reiteration allows the beneficiaries and the RWLs to understand and more successfully work with the existing risk governance structures, and -where necessary and possible - improve the existing risk governance structures. The lessons learned from the application of the initial and the further developed Risk-Tandem Framework in the four RWLs allows for the identification of cross-cutting issues and mechanism for improved governance and interoperability to support DRR and CCA in general.

WP 3's focus on the governance of DRR and CCA in the RWLs means that it is methodologically situated within social sciences and economics, both qualitative and quantitative, as well as the humanities more generally. These disciplines provide the necessary frameworks, methods, and tools for gathering and processing research data, e.g. through surveys, interactive workshops, serious games, etc. as well as the theoretical groundwork to contextualize and meaningfully interpret the gathered information. The close collaboration with the modellers within the DIRECTED Project and the RWL has consequently produced an interdisciplinary framework for the assessment, management, and governance of DRR and CCA that is founded on a conceptual understanding of risk governance, institutional development and science, technology, and society discourses surrounding co-creative knowledge production. In the following stages of the project, this conceptual understanding will be informed by empirical and modelling data through the close collaboration with IIASA and PIK.

In sum, through the Risk-Tandem Framework and the constant engagement with the RWLs, WP 3 seeks

- to understand how risk governance is currently executed in the RWLs,
- to systematically assess risk governance in the RWLs by means of criteria and indicators derived from the Risk-Tandem Framework,
- to reflect on and improve the Risk-Tandem Framework, and
- to help improve risk governance in the RWLs and beyond through knowledge integration and co-production.

1.2.3.2 Progress per task

The following table lists the WP 3's objectives, gives a description and update on their status:

Table 4: Summary of deliverables, milestones, and tasks status in WP 3.

Deliverables, Milestones, and Tasks	Status report
M12 – Scoping consultations with RWLs	<p>Status: Met</p> <p>Scoping consultations with the RWLs and mapping of the RWL's governance context (for detailed information, see below under "RWL Engagement Meetings")</p>
D3.1 – Risk-Tandem Framework	<p>Status: Submitted, under external review</p> <p>Developing an innovative and integrated risk governance framework for DRR and CCA (Risk-Tandem Framework)</p> <p>WP 3 has complied with the workplan and produced Risk-Tandem (D3.1), a risk governance framework for DRR and CCA that rests on conceptually sound and empirically validated approaches towards risk governance, stakeholder engagement, and knowledge co-production. The close collaboration with both the RWLs as well as the modelling partners from the project assured that the Risk-Tandem Framework does not only make a valuable contribution to risk governance and risk management scholarship, but that the framework can also be directly applied and be of use in the RWLs.</p>
D3.2 – Updated Risk-Tandem Framework for governance processes and interoperability	<p>Status: Work in Progress</p> <p>Applying and testing the Risk-Tandem Framework empirically in Real World Labs (RWL) to facilitate the co-development and sustained application of risk models and tools via the interoperable platform.</p> <p>The central objective of WP 3 is to develop, apply, and adapt an integrative risk governance framework for the respective needs of the RWLs and beyond. With the first Task (3.1) being achieved, the focus for the beneficiaries now lies with the application and real-world/practical testing of the Risk-Tandem Framework (Task 3.2). While collaboration with the RWLs and other WPs has been central throughout Task 3.1 already, further close interaction with the RWLs will be crucial to achieve the objectives set out in Task 3.2 and beyond. The co-creative aspects of T3.2 will be achieved through qualitative data collection processes, such as a Q-Survey and a Capacity Needs Assessment, interactive workshops, and serious games initiated and developed by colleagues from WP 4 in collaboration with WP 3. These engagement tools will on the one hand allow for a testing of the Risk-Tandem Framework, and on the other hand give space for feedback, reiterations, and improvements.</p>
D3.3 – Policy brief on risk governance in the context of DRR and CCA	<p>Status: Planned</p> <p>Publishing and sharing of tested and improved Risk-Tandem Framework that supports coherent and integrated DRR and CCA planning and decision-making processes and builds long-term</p>

	<p>governance capacity for information and knowledge integration</p> <p>Throughout the process of achieving the objectives set out in both T3.1 and T3.2, concurrent steps are being taken to meet the requirements of T3.3. With regard to the publication and sharing of a refined Risk-Tandem Framework, a number of academic articles are currently in production throughout beneficiaries involved in WP 3. Furthermore, a number of the beneficiaries are planning to present and disseminate the framework in various salient conferences in their respective research areas.</p>
<p>D3.4 – Guidance on good practices regarding interoperability of governance mechanisms and recommendations for institutionalising project outcomes and the interoperable platform into existing systems</p>	<p>Status: Planned</p> <p>Identifying a tailored governance mechanism based on the Risk-Tandem Framework’s application to guide and sustain the knowledge exchange between targeted users beyond the project and enable co-ownership with targeted users</p> <p>Similarly, the objective of guiding and sustaining the knowledge exchange between researchers and practitioners set out by Task 3.4, while still in early development, is being slowly worked towards through close and active engagement with the RWLs and their local stakeholders.</p>

Task 3.1 Framework Development (Month 1 – 16) (Lead: RIFS (GFZ), co-lead SEI, contributors: IIASA and UCC)

Regarding the state-of-the-art scholarship on risk governance, the increasing complexities and interdependencies of current risk landscapes demand integrated approaches towards risk governance that surpass current practice which rests to a large extent on siloed and fragmented approaches towards risk governance and risk management. Indeed, there is a need to strive towards adaptive and transformative governance that can, on one hand, manage systemic issues through knowledge integration, and on the other hand, cope with uncertainty (Hochrainer-Stigler, et al., 2023¹; Sillmann, et al., 2022²; Berkes, 2017³; Renn and Schweizer, 2009⁴). Yet it is still a contested issue how these aspirations translate into policies and concrete action (Deubelli and Mechler, 2021⁵). To address these questions, the Risk-Tandem Framework (D3.1) integrates various methods and approaches for the management of complexity and systemic risks, all the while relying on qualitative and quantitative data. The Risk-Tandem Framework therefore builds on state-of-the-art risk governance and management tools, while also serving as an integrated approach wherein the synthesized sum of its various methods is greater than the individual approaches that make up the framework.

Task 3.2 also requires that the Risk-Tandem Framework actively include solutions for data interoperability. This requirement will be fulfilled through collaboration with WP 2, drawing on

¹Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Deubelli-Hwang, T. M., Mechler, R., Dieckmann, U., Lauerien, F. and Handmer, J. (2023) ‘Closing the ‘Operationalisation Gap’: Insights from Systemic Risk Research to Inform Transformational Adaptation and Risk Management’, *Climate Risk Management*

²Sillmann, J., Christensen, I., Hochrainer-Stigler, S., Huang-Lachman, J-T., Juhola, S., Kornhuber, K., Mahecha, M. D., Mechler, R., Reichstein, M., Ruane, A. C., Schweizer, P.-J., and Williams, S. (2022) Briefing Note on Systemic Risk: Review and Opportunities for Research, Policy and Practice from the Perspective of Climate, Environmental and Disaster Risk Science and Management, Geneva: UNDRR

³Berkes, F. (2017) ‘Environmental Governance for the Anthropocene? Social-Ecological Systems, Resilience and Collaborative Learning’, *Sustainability*, 9(7)

⁴Renn, O. and Schweizer, P.-J. (2009) ‘Inclusive Risk Governance: Concepts and Application to Environmental Policy Making’, *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 19(3), pp. 174-185

⁵Deubelli, T. M. and Mechler, R. (2021) ‘Perspectives on Transformational Change in Climate Risk Management and Adaptation’, *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(5), pp. 53002

the expertise gathered through the creation of a robust Data Fabric by that Work Package. The methodological link to combine the Data Fabric and quantitative risk assessments with the Risk-Tandem Framework will be built on the Risk Layering approach laid out in, among others, D3.1.

A direct application of the concepts from the Institutional Analysis and Development framework will further help evaluate and improve the theoretical assumptions that play a central role for the assessment, management, and governance of disaster risks and climate change adaptation. The development and implementation of a set of indicators will allow the Risk-Tandem Framework to handle questions such as, how are vulnerabilities defined in the respective RWLs, what values and norms play a role in the various institutional set-ups, and what kinds of structures increase or reduce disaster risks. For this reason, and the further development of the Risk-Tandem Framework, meetings between WP 3, WP 4, and the RWL leads are taking place:

Coordination Meetings between WP 3 and WP 4:

WP 3 meetings have enabled the conceptual development of the Risk-Tandem Framework and supported initial risk governance analysis in the RWLs. To support overall coordination between WP 3 and WP 4, weekly meetings were established since January 2023, allowing for the smooth alignment of tasks, activities and deliverables. The initial framework and supporting visualisations for the Risk-Tandem Framework emerged from a week-long research visit of SEI in-person (20-24th January 2023) to UCC in Cork, Ireland and supported by RIFS joining online.

RWL Engagement Meetings:

The Risk-Tandem Framework will ultimately act as an approach for the Real World Labs to use to support an integrated DRR/CCA governance assessment through methods of co-production. As such, Task 3.1 Risk-Tandem Framework development and 3.2 Risk-Tandem Framework implementation are intertwined and strong efforts to actively interact with RWL around Risk-Tandem before the start of Task 3.2. Furthermore, given the integral nature of WP 4 tasks on knowledge co-production and capacity development to the Risk-Tandem Framework, researchers in WP 3 and WP 4 worked in parallel to introduce and guide the RWLs around the Risk-Tandem Framework to support the RWLs to understand the risk governance context (focus of WP 3) and implementing knowledge co-production (focus WP 4). Consultation meetings took place with Capital Region of Denmark (17th Feb 2023) and Rhine-Erft (13th March 2023) RWLs, a jour-fix presentation was made to other RWLs to introduce the initial framework and answer related questions (16 March 2023). RWLs were provided with resources on the Risk-Tandem Framework including a recorded video, presentation, briefing note, risk governance assessment guiding questions (focus for WP 3) and facilitation guide (focus WP 4) to inform their RWL stakeholder engagement and initial workshop activities. WP 3 again in collaboration with WP 4, continued engagement with RWL hosts by offering workshop debriefing meetings to reflect on their workshops and offer guidance and support going forward to advance risk governance and knowledge co-production in their RWLs. These took place with Capital Region of Denmark (9th March 2023 and 25th August 2023), Emilia-Romagna Region (30th March, during Jour Fixe and 16th October 2023) and Rhine-Erft Region (21st April 2023) and the Danube Region (12th June 2023).

Figure 9: Impressions from the stakeholder workshops and training the trainers.

To support integration of Risk-Tandem into the WP 4 task on knowledge co-production training, between June and September 2023, UCC and SEI met weekly to develop Risk-Tandem related training activities for the Directed General Assembly in Cologne (18th - 21st September 2023). These events focused on helping the RWLs to unravel the risk governance barriers and enables through needs and opportunity mapping (focus WP 3) and skills development around knowledge co-production using serious games, creative play and world cafes (focus of WP 4). WP 3 supported scoping interviews for capacity development with RWLs, led by WP 4, with the specific WP 3 aim to capture recent insights on their risk governance context, level of stakeholder engagement, and understand their needs for support around Risk-Tandem (e.g. further explaining the Risk-Tandem Framework to new RWL colleagues). These scoping interviews took place with the Capital Region of Denmark (13th December 2023), Rhine-Erft Region (22nd Jan 2024), Emilia-Romagna Region (23rd Jan 2024) and Danube Region (14th Dec 2023).

Task 3.2 Applying a merged framework (RISK-TANDEM) to Real World Labs (Month 12-36) (lead: RIFS, co-lead: UCC, contributors: IIASA, SEI, GFZ, PIK, DTU, GECO, OASIS, 52N, G&C)

In terms of partially completed tasks, Task 3.2 is currently being worked on by the project partners involved in WP 3. As per the description in the grant agreement, Task 3.2 involves applying and refining the Risk-Tandem Framework for the governance processes and interoperability, focusing on its application within the RWLs. This entails applying and testing the framework empirically in the RWLs to facilitate the co-development and sustained application of risk models and tools via the interoperable platform.

All the interactions with the RWL as described in Task 3.1 provided the groundwork for the implementation of the Risk-Tandem Framework with the RWLs. On the 30th of January UCC researcher visited Copenhagen for a day-long planning meeting with their RWL to support their RWL stakeholder engagement and risk governance analysis.

The implementation of Risk-Tandem requires connectivity with the risk-related data, models and tools being explored in WP 2 and the Data Fabric being developed in WP 5 to ensure integration between the governance, communication and data/modelling systems. To facilitate alignment, researchers from WP 3 attend WP 2 meetings related to interoperability, e.g. the meeting on 16th October 2023.

Various meetings with individual project partners and other WPs have been held, and collaboration will continue to achieve the interoperability side of the objective set out in 3.2. Specifically, the Risk Layering approach will play a central role to bridge the gap between quantitative modelling approaches and qualitative assessment processes, ensuring that information and data retrieved by either side can be used meaningfully for the integrated assessment of both DRR and CCA. Further, future meetings with the individual RWLs are planned to apply the Risk-Tandem Framework to the various problem situations that the regions face. This will help tailor the framework more precisely to the needs of each RWL.

Task 3.3 Evaluating RISK-TANDEM and Lessons Learnt (Month 33-48) (lead: GFZ (RIFS), co-lead: UCC, contributors: SEI, IIASA)

This task has not yet begun but will involve evaluating the effectiveness of the risk governance mechanisms identified in Task 3.2 for strengthening multi-stakeholder engagement, interoperability and knowledge exchange. The task will also involve improving the Risk-Tandem Framework based on evidence and learning from RWLs. The activities in this task are closely aligned to Task 1.3 focusing on the evaluation and outcomes/ impact monitoring of the RWLs, also led by RIFS.

1.2.4 Work Package 4 – Knowledge co-production

1.2.4.1 Introduction

WP 4 focuses on bridging connections between different disciplines and knowledge systems toward integrated DRR, CCA and systemic risk management with the support of iterative knowledge co-production and associated capacity development. Methodologically, this work has built upon SEI's expertise in capacity development and knowledge co-production, informed by the SEI-developed Tandem Framework (Daniels et al., 2020, Bharwani et al., 2024)⁶.

WP 4 continues to expand the discourse on knowledge co-production and its application in sustainability sciences with the support of contemporary literature and state-of-the-art knowledge on risk governance, DRR, CCA and systemic risk management (WP 3). Despite the theoretical complexity (necessary for addressing complex socio-ecological risks), WP 4 remains committed to practice, providing tools, activities, capacity development, and workshops that can support the RWLs in producing “useful” and actionable knowledge through transdisciplinary collaboration, to increase the capacity of actors to create shared understanding, solutions and commitments to risk management. WP 4s approaches are also leveraged to assess, understand and translate user needs through taxonomy development (WP 2) resulting in a planned glossary for the Data Fabric (WP 5) to create a shared understanding of the models, their uses and results. Finally, these tasks contribute to developing a science-informed knowledge base for operationalizing knowledge co-production in integrated risk management, disseminated in collaboration with WP 6 (as discussed in D6.3 Gaps and Opportunities Assessment for Knowledge Transfer).

The work carried out by WP 4 is manifold and contributes to SO3 and SO4. It cuts across different work streams and deliverables to support capacities in enabling knowledge co-production. In terms of RWL engagements (WP 1), WP 4 identifies and supports the hosts of each lab through a Training of Trainers programme (D1.2. Capacity Development Strategy for DIRECTED), seeking to mainstream knowledge co-production in existing working arrangements in a locally led manner. In other words, capacity development informs the integration of co-production into existing governance arrangements (WP 3). This supports RWL hosts to create and strengthen relationships, networks and to develop a shared understanding of challenges and solutions through transdisciplinary engagement. Efforts to deliver DIRECTED ambitions on integrated DRR, CCA, and systemic risk management in their social and technical dimensions are part of this process. Tasks in WP 4 are highly integrated with WP 3 and within the Risk-Tandem Framework (D3.1), in efforts to continuously and iteratively align knowledge co-production with the risk governance context and emerging needs. Co-production approaches are also applied to identify and map user needs, and build connections between modellers (WP 2) and end users of risk/climate data to inform the development of the Data Fabric (WP 5).

Consistent efforts have been made throughout this period to compliment the work of partners in WPs 1, - 6, including RIFS (providing insights to risk governance and management), UCC (stakeholder engagement, knowledge transfer and participatory governance), and IIASA (integrated Risk Layering for the quantitative analysis of hazards and decision making processes).

⁶Daniels, Elizabeth, et al. "Refocusing the climate services lens: Introducing a framework for co-designing “transdisciplinary knowledge integration processes” to build climate resilience." *Climate Services* 19 (2020): 100181.

1.2.4.2 Progress per task

WP 4 and SEI have worked closely with WP 1 and the RWLs. A good relationship with RWL hosts and stakeholders and deep understanding of the RWL context is required to enable the integration of co-production mechanisms into existing risk governance arrangements (and to understand where they could be complemented with the provision of new ones). Consultations, interviews, surveys and other scoping exercises have also been conducted to ensure that the work of partners is informed by RWL needs, and that the capacity development training aligns with the ambitions of Risk-Tandem (WP 3). The following table describes WP 4 objectives, including its description and an update on current status:

Table 5: Summary of deliverables, milestones, and tasks status in WP 4.

Deliverables, Milestones and Tasks	Status report
D4.1. Capacity Development Modules for Training of Trainers (month 36)	<p>Status: In progress</p> <p>Aligning with D1.2. and Risk-Tandem, D4.1 seeks to develop the capacities of RWL hosts in enabling and designing knowledge co-production processes in their risk governance contexts. One module is already developed and delivered, and webinars linking to capacity development are planned to take place in Q1 of 2024. Modules that are developed will be made available online on we-ADAPT by M32.</p>
Milestone 15	<p>Lays the foundation for further periodic reporting (M16-18) and D4.3 (M48) by: 1) explaining the conceptual framework and underpinning the design of co-production process; 2) collating experiences and challenges regarding co-production; 3) reviewing progress from the RWLs; 4) documenting the methodology that will be used to analyze and update the Tandem framework (M16-18); and, 5) providing recommendations for strengthening the Tandem cycle.</p>
Task 4.2	<p>Status: In progress</p> <p>Capacity development individual engagements, training, and workshops developed in parallel with T1.2.</p>
D4.2. Framework for Distilling Different Assumptions in Different Modelling Approaches with Recommendations for Replication (month 42)	<p>Status: Planned</p> <p>Developed based on discussions around trade-offs and assumptions in the models, for improved interoperability and iterative development based on user needs. Seeks to support further replication.</p>
Milestone 19 - Scoping consultation with RWL and mapping of capacity development needs begins	<p>Status: In progress</p> <p>Meeting minutes from scoping consultations for mapping capacity development needs. These were supposed to begin formally by month 9, but the first semi-structured interviews took place in month 15-16.</p>
D4.3 Updated (tested and refined) Tandem Cycle for Transdisciplinary Knowledge co-production (month 48)	<p>Status: In progress</p> <p>Improving and refining the Tandem co-production cycle based on emerging evidence from the RWLs, in efforts to support the further application of Tandem in risk governance contexts.</p>

Task 4.1 Apply the Tandem knowledge co-production cycle to the RWL (Month 6-45) (lead: SEI, co-lead: GECO, contributors: RIFS, UCC, GFZ, PIK, DTU, IIASA)

SEI has led the delivery of D1.2. (Capacity Building Strategy for DIRECTED), and contributed to the D3.1. describing the Risk-Tandem (integrative and iterative risk governance framework for holistic DRR, CCA and systemic risk management). These two deliverables were designed closely together and through continuous consultation with partners, to ensure that capacity development also supports the practical implementation of the Risk-Tandem by the RWL partners. In more detail, SEI's role is to examine and translate the tools and approaches provided by WP 3 in practice by delivering and refining them through the lens of co-production and co-design (structuring their application via Tandem), in efforts to make sure they are fit for purpose in the RWL context.

Building on this context, WP 4 delivered its first module for D4.1 on 'Complex risk and Knowledge co-production' that acted as an introduction to the Risk-Tandem Framework. Although it preceded the submission of Deliverable D3.1 (Risk-Tandem), WPs 3 and 4 collaborated closely to ensure that they remain conceptually and practically aligned by informing D4.1 with literature reviews. Modules on facilitation skills and research skills including monitoring and evaluation are in progress. Other consultations and scoping exercises are planned for later in 2024, to further inform capacity development modules based on emerging RWL needs.

WP 4 has also closely engaged with the RWLs and WP 1 throughout this process to support their operationalization and set-up (M2/M3/D1.1.), and build upon this collaboration to inform the conceptual development of the strategies and frameworks with emerging needs and evidence. Further, WP 4 continued to support WP 3 in launching the Risk-Tandem Framework (including delivering its first module on understanding and co-exploring complex risks in a multi-hazard setting, and how this could be implemented in the RWLs). Tools for co-exploring risks as introduced in the module were later taken up by RWL 2 in their workshop with positive results; the debriefing described the co-productive mode as vastly more efficient way of working than more 'traditional' presentations and exchanges.

Having complied with the delivery of D1.2. in 2023, WP 4 activities related to capacity development have focussed on: M15 (applying knowledge co-production and training of trainers in alignment with Risk-Tandem, phased according to the Tandem cycle steps) and continuing M15. (scoping consultations to support capacity development modules, and activities).

WP 1/RWL Coordination meetings: As described under WP 3 regarding meetings, the integrated nature of tasks associated with the application of Risk-Tandem and knowledge co-production in RWLs necessitates close coordination between RWLs and researchers from WPs 3/4. As such most consultation meetings are shared to minimize stakeholder fatigue and to maximize benefits for both WPs (although meeting focus is decided beforehand to identify which partner it will benefit the most). See joint meeting and description in table in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** for WP 4 reference (detailing work pertaining to capacity development, knowledge co-production, and engagement with the RWLs in relation to Risk-Tandem).

Task 4.2 RWL comparison and assessment of needs through learning, capacity development and knowledge exchange (Month 9-36) (lead: SEI, co-lead: 52N, contributors: RIFS, GECO, UCC, GFZ, PIK, DTU, IIASA, GC)

Task 4.2 is advancing novel innovation related to capacity development, especially in terms of responding to the capacity needs assessment (D1.2) with practical guidance and impact monitoring. In addition, the first progress report under M15 will lay the foundation for monitoring and evaluating knowledge co-production processes across the RWLs (e.g. contributing to D1.3).

WP 4/3 coordination meetings: WPs 3 and 4 collaborate closely to co-design and co-deploy the Risk-Tandem Framework, in efforts to better align risk governance approaches, knowledge co-production, and capacity development. To enable this, weekly meetings have taken place since January 2023. Literature reviews and research toward D1.2 and D3.1 and associated milestones (3/15/19) have been led jointly by researchers in WPs 3 and 4 to maximize their impacts and effectiveness.

Task 4.3 Distil relevant climate and non-climate information for the tools and Data Fabric (Month 12-42) (lead: SEI, co-lead: 52N, contributors: GECO, RIFS, GECO, UCC, GFZ, PIK, DTU, IIASA)

In terms of connecting to WP 2 (taxonomy) and WP 5 (Data Fabric), WP 4 has participated in meetings with modelling teams to better understand their capabilities and the degree to which they address the needs of stakeholders in the RWLs. More specifically, WP 4 has bridged connections with WP 5 which has begun to explore existing standards, models and tools and to scope out RWL data needs (T2.1), and contributed to the design of the scoping questionnaire and interviews. This is part of the distillation process to identify relevant climate and non-climate information for input to the models and Data Fabric.

WP 4/WP 5 Coordination meetings: WP 4 has also sought to engage with WP 5 in efforts to support the co-design and eventual co-development of the Data Fabric toward increased data interoperability. Alongside contributing to task 2.1, it has joined consultation meetings intending to scope the interoperability context between WP 5 and RWLs.

Task 4.4: Updating and improving the Tandem knowledge co-production cycle based on empirical evidence generated in RWL (Month 6-48) (lead: SEI, co-lead: 52North)

Following the implementation and analysis of questionnaires under T2.1 focusing on data interoperability needs, WP 4 has employed a Q-survey to explore the RWL perceptions, knowledges and values in relation to risk governance and knowledge co-production. The survey seeks to understand gaps in understanding between partners and RWLs, and will build on this evidence to further improve the implementation of the (Risk)-Tandem cycle.

WP 4 will further embed knowledge co-production into risk governance through capacity development informed by emerging needs through T2.1./M17/M13 (engaging with RWLs in a co-productive mode with WPs 1 and 3). Further, it will continue to bridge connections between RWLs and work packages and use evidence generated by WP 3 to identify opportunities for enabling co-production and addressing associated challenges in RWL workshops. Conversely, co-production processes will enable the identification of strengths and weaknesses in the each RWL governance landscape and decision-making context.

1.2.5 Work Package 5 – Data Fabric

1.2.5.1 Introduction

Work Package 5 – Data Fabric – designs, develops and provides the infrastructure to demonstrate the impact of an improved interoperability in the context of DRM and CCA. This Work Package stretches over the entire project span, where Tasks 5.1 and 5.2 are the only tasks addressed in this reporting period and focus on the stocktaking of existing process, data and models supporting the requirement analysis being the foundation of the co-design. Later, the co-developed Data Fabric will showcase the benefit of increased sharing, availability and aggregation of data for increased resilience and more effective disaster warning and response. The aforementioned platform will thereby serve as a framework for other European countries and projects, in how interoperability, governance, information, and data, can come together to create a lasting channel of data-sharing tools and technologies.

1.2.5.2 Progress per task

WP 5 did not have any Milestones or Deliverables in RP1. The work has been concentrated in Tasks 5.1 and 5.2.

Table 6: Summary of deliverables, milestones, and tasks status in WP 5.

Deliverables, Milestones and Tasks	Status report
Task 5.1 Month 1–21	After the RWL had been established, the requirement analysis has been initiated based on dedicated meetings per RWL and guided interviews. Results build the foundation of the design of the DIRECTED Data Fabric. This task is still ongoing and no Milestones or Deliverables had been planned for the first reporting period.
Task 5.2 Month 1–24	Together with the modelling partners of DIRECTED and based on the needs and current procedures of the RWLs, different interoperability use cases that could be showcased in the DIRECTED Data Fabric have been developed and discussed. This task is still ongoing and no Milestones or Deliverables had been planned for the first reporting period.
Task 5.3	First actions have been taken. The integration of additional components (i.e. EFAS, GloFAS and the Copernicus Climate Data Store) into the Data Fabric is currently assessed in two RWLs.
Task 5.4	The work on this task has not started yet, but is scheduled for the upcoming reporting period
D5.1 (Month 21)	The High Level Design Document – Data Fabric will be created in Task 5.3 during the upcoming reporting period.
D5.2 (Month 24)	The Low Level Design Document Data Fabric will be created in Task 5.3 during the upcoming reporting period.
D5.3 (Month 24)	The Data Protection Impact Assessment will be created in Task 5.3 and 5.4 during the upcoming reporting period.
D5.4 (Month 24)	The Implementation documentation will be created in Task 5.4

Task 5.1 – Stocktaking of the Current Data Context (Month 1-21) (lead: 52N, co-lead: GECO, contributors: OASIS, UCC, IIASA, RWL partners) – has started in month one and is still ongoing. Workshops with the RWL leading teams have been held to raise a common understanding on the current situation and needs of the different RWLs. Those meetings have been held mostly online and separately with each RWL. During the discussions, a high level understanding of the entire workflows from the data sources, through the modelling chains to the information product was gained. The figure below gives an example of a preliminary framework for the components in RWL Danube. These meetings have been integral to the relationship with the RWLs, as WP 5 was able to collect the specific information needs of the end users who will interact with the platform. These efforts are directed towards the creation of high level Design Document for the Data Fabric (D5.1, see Figure 72) due to be delivered in June 2024 to reach Milestone 21.

Figure 10: High-level Concept of the Data Fabric.

On August 17, 2023, a team of WP 5 met with the **Danube RWL**. In this meeting, we covered topics such as the RWL’s current status, the stakeholder needs, and the upgraded model which is to be implemented for this RWL. Since this lab also covers a particularly large area of the EU, including Romania, Croatia, Serbia, Austria, Hungary, and Slovenia, it was important for this RWL to have concise contacts within a few key countries in the region, so that data needs and implementation could be put forth in a streamlined effort. Thus, in this RWL, the main countries defining the requirements (with stakeholders in contact with this RWL), are Serbia, Austria, and Hungary. In Austria the focus is specifically on Vienna with the Austrian Red Cross, and in Hungary the main focus is on the Zala Region, with insurance industries. In this meeting we also had an in-depth discussion regarding the main model which will be implemented for this RWL, this model being the Danube Model, formerly known as the Future Danube Model (FDM). The discussion on the Danube Model was very helpful, and provided new avenues of exploration regarding the platform’s architecture (see Figure 80).

Based on the insights from ongoing Tasks 5.1 and 5.2, the discussions with users and modellers, a high level conceptual model of the Data Fabric has been developed, presented and discussed. The Data Fabric shall be designed as a federated, yet seamlessly integrated infrastructure. The development of Data Spaces has made considerable progress since the proposal phase of DIRECTED and the underlying concept of Data Spaces has been reviewed in the context of CCA and DRR. It is foreseen, that the Data Fabric shall be compatible with the concept of Data Spaces.

In order to make better informed decisions about the technical design and implementation of the DIRECTED Data Fabric, different components have been assessed in small defined sub-use-cases, as e.g. in the Emilia-Romagna and Rhine-Erft RWLs. The results from those two case studies will serve as a framework for the rest of the platform implementation, thus providing the requirements for **Task 5.3** (starting in July 2024). One eminent use case that emerged from the discussions with the RWLs was the use and integration of data from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS). In particular, the European and Global Flood Awareness Systems (EFAS, GloFAS) were assessed for the integration into the Data Fabric.

In terms of the current reporting period, no Milestones nor Deliverables had been planned; however the upcoming Deliverable D5.1 “High Level Design Document – Data Fabric” is in preparation.

1.2.6 Work Package 6 – Communication and Dissemination

1.2.6.1 Introduction

The objectives of Work Package 6 - Communications, dissemination, exploitation and impact as outlined in the grant agreement are as follows:

To develop appropriate communication, dissemination, learning, education, training and exploitation for all stakeholders linked to aims for integrating risk assessment, risk governance and management, climate adaptation planning, communication and operational tools and systems for coping with extreme climate events.

Objectives are:

- Expanding capabilities to communicate, utilize and exchange state-of-the-art data, information and knowledge between actors.
- Boosting the integration, accessibility, and interoperability of models to actors.
- Facilitating an enhanced community engagement and developing new governance and risk management strategies using a bottom-up, value-driven co-development approach.
- Developing routes to market scaling via business plan development for the public and private sector

1.2.6.2 Progress per task

Table 7: Summary of deliverables, milestones, and tasks status in WP 6.

Deliverables, Milestones and Tasks	Status and comments
Deliverable D6.1 DIRECTED Communication and Dissemination Strategy Task 6.1 Milestone 26	Status: Submitted A broad communications and dissemination plan was prepared by all the beneficiary organisations. D6.1 was prepared with two main aspects. This included an overriding DIRECTED Project communications and dissemination strategy and then a detailed plan at beneficiary level included in the submitted D6.1 Strategy. The strategy has included a range of targeted communications and dissemination activities including branding, website, social media, videos and webinars with broad timings for the delivery of the plan, based around the project cycle. In addition, the plan outlines the objectives and impacts expected as a result of the DIRECTED Project. It also presents communications and dissemination objectives and impacts will be monitored. Completion of this task also leads to the completion of Milestone 26.
Deliverable D6.2 DIRECTED Communication and Dissemination Report	Status: Submitted D6.2 Communications and Dissemination Report 1 - evidences the communication and dissemination work conducted during the period from Oct 2022 to End of Sept 2023 (Yr 1) of the project.

Task 6.2	<p>The report outlines the work conducted during the first year of the project which relates to setting up specific communications venues including branding, development of branded assets (logos and project branded reporting and poster templates), social media channel set-up and introductory project film. It also outlines work completed under each communications and dissemination channel by all beneficiaries and links to evidence of work where possible.</p> <p>In addition, we have also developed a DIRECTED Storyboard to assist DIRECTED partners in building communications targeting specific target groups using methodologies that they most respond to. For instance MPs are more likely to engage with direct letters, academia and scientists through academic papers and conferences, disaster professionals through LinkedIn etc. The Storyboard can be found here: https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVNcLaYD8=/</p>
Deliverable D6.3. Gaps and Opportunities assessment Task 6.3	<p>Status: Submitted</p> <p>Task 6.3 involved outlining the Gaps and Opportunities for Knowledge Transfer within the Directed project and D6.3 puts forward a Knowledge Transfer Plan including 1) Key exploitable results, 2) Knowledge transfer mechanisms, 3) Target groups, and 4) Impact pathway.</p>
Deliverable D6.4 e Learning Portal Milestone 27 Task 6.4	<p>Status: Planned (due month 45)</p> <p>An on-line repository containing all the learning materials co-designed and developed with stakeholders for training and educational related programmes (developed as part of Task 6.4, in progress) will be hosted on an established, appropriate website. D6.3 outlines possible options for such portals and the types of resources that can be made available.</p>
Deliverable D6.5 Business Development Plan Task 6.6	<p>Status: Planned (due month 48)</p> <p>This plan will act as the main exploitation road-map and strategy.</p>
Deliverable D6.6 Communications report 2 Task 6.2	<p>Status: Underway</p> <p>A Project Level Communications Plan for the current year (October, 2023 to September, 2024) can be found here and guides the work for this year. See planning tool here: https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMMvAd8w=/</p> <p>Good progress is underway as planned in the DIRECTED Communication and Dissemination Report 1.</p>
Deliverable D6.7 Communications report 3	Not due.
Deliverable D6.8 Communications report 4	Not due
D6.9 Legacy document on the capacity/ skills for risk and adaptation management Task 6.5	<p>Status: Planned (due month 36)</p> <p>Recommendations on how capacity/ skills related evolving pathways in the development of governance and technological frameworks (Risk-Tandem and Data Fabric) can address challenges of risk and adaptation management. This learning will be generated from Task 6.5 (tracking and evaluation of learning programmes) and in collaboration with WP 4 implementing the capacity</p>

development strategy and learning modules for RWLs.

Task 6.1 - Develop a communication strategy for the directed project and thereafter communication updates for relevant reporting cycles (Month 1-4) (Lead: OASIS, Contributors: All)

The D6.1 Communications and Dissemination Strategy was developed to ensure a detailed plan of communications and dissemination for both the DIRECTED Project overall and beneficiary communications planning related to the project was completed. A comprehensive communications and dissemination programme, that engages, informs and influences our target audiences and enables us to move towards our outcomes and longer term impacts was developed.

Specifically, our target audiences include:

1. First and second responders
2. Regional and municipal civil authorities - including disaster management, planning authorities and cross regional municipalities
3. Physical and social scientific organisations - those who work in climate change, natural disaster sciences and damage and loss, governance and innovation
4. The general public - will be represented by municipalities

The programme and tasks are based around the stages of the Project as per Table 8 below.

Table 8: DIRECTED communications timeline.

Phase 1 Oct 2022 to March 2023	Phase 2 March 2023 to March 2024	Phase 3 March 2024 to March 2025	Phase 4 March 2025 to March 2026	Phase 5 March 2026 to October 2026
Communications strategy developed Project launch communications Start of Project Blog – quarterly blog posts to continue to end of the Project Bi-weekly social media posts began and continued to the end of the Project e.g. stories, plans etc. Website development Brand development	Communications on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project events ● Workshops ● Processes and techniques and the physical and social scientists/ themselves ● Building a picture of the people involved in Directed stakeholder involvement and outcomes during this phase Continued social media dissemination Beginning of conference dissemination	Communications on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Early scientific & governance and process ● Findings from market research and stakeholder needs assessment ● Real World Lab reports Continued conference dissemination Continued social media dissemination Case study creation	Research publications and related news and articles Training material and programme on use of tools and systems Webinar series with physical and social scientists Continued social media dissemination Media pack creation & dissemination (press releases for international media)	Policy-maker meetings, policy briefs. Conference dissemination of results Continued social media dissemination

The report includes our plans on the Project including under Communications - Launch, Project Branding & Website development, Real World Labs and Case Study Development, visualisations, Social Media, Video, Podcasts and Webinars, a Quarterly Blog, Mass Media and Media Pack Creation. Dissemination plans include - Tool demonstrations, Stakeholder

Engagement – co-design and co-development, Policy briefs and Policy-Maker meetings, DIRECTED e-Learning Portal, Published Papers, Conference Attendance and use of EU Communications and Dissemination Platforms. Each section included specific targets and indicators and the Outcomes aided by the communication or dissemination action. This report also states our monitoring and evaluation strategy linked to communications and dissemination and therefore the document can be used to track the success of individual actions.

Task 6.2 Deliver a full communication programme (Month 3-48) (Lead OASIS, Contributors: All) At the end of each project year a Communications and Dissemination Report is developed to track the communications and dissemination actions and to plan for the next year. As the Project is four years long, four reports will be due by the end of the Project. As we are still relatively early in the Project, we have completed one report D6.2 Communications and Dissemination Report Yr1. This report tracks and evidences the communications and dissemination work, and as far as possible, tracks the M&E parameters outlined in the D6.1 Communications and Dissemination Strategy, as well as tracks progress to Project Outcomes and longer term Impacts. At this point we have completed detailed tracking of communications and dissemination activities for the Period Oct 2022 to Sept 2023 – as per grant agreement. This can be seen in the submitted report for Year 1 (which can be accessed through the EU Grants Portal) and therefore we have not replicated that for the purpose of this report. We are part way through Yr 2 and plans can be found both in the D6.2 Yr 1 report and [here](#).

Highlights for the period between October 2022 to End of Jan 2024 include:

Website development and analytics

Max Steinhausen (TUBS) and Tracy Irvine (OASIS) designed and developed our Project website found here: <https://directedproject.eu/>. The website was built by SpitzBub, selected after a formal tender process by TUBS. We have designed it to be visually simple and easy to follow and locate information about the project.

We are now able to track detailed activity on the website as we have implemented google analytics as follows which gives an indication on how well we are growing our online traffic. We refer to Figure 12 and Figure 96 for detailed statistics.

Most Popular Content Export

Post/Page	URL	Post Type	Views	Proportion
Home Page	/		4,691	59.91 %
About	/about/	Page	1,652	21.10 %
Media	/media/	Page	594	7.59 %
News	/news/	Page	171	2.18 %
/blog/real-world-lab-capital-region-of-denmark/	/blog/real-world-lab-capital-region-of-denmark/		118	1.51 %
Blog	/blog/	Page	114	1.46 %
Moving out of the silos	/blog/moving-out-of-the-silos/	Blog	110	1.40 %
Breaking the Silos towards knowledge co-production in Real World Labs using Serious Games	/blog/breaking-the-silos-towards-knowledge-co-production-in-real-world-lab/	Blog	89	1.14 %
Product Solutions	/product-solutions/	Page	72	0.92 %
Privacy	/privacy/	Page	33	0.42 %
The DIRECTED Project is developing a taxonomy of terminologies used by local communities for climate risk and resilience, improving the 'Connectivity Hub' developed by the Stockholm Environment Institute	/blog/the-directed-project-is-developing-a-taxonomy-of-terminologies-used-by-local-communities-for-climate-risk-and-resilience-improving-the-connectivity-hub-developed-by-the-stockholm-e/	Blog	32	0.41 %
/news/kick-off-meeting-in-braunschweig/	/news/kick-off-meeting-in-braunschweig/		26	0.33 %
Imprint	/imprint/	Page	23	0.29 %
Real World Lab – The Capital Region of Denmark	/blog/real-world-lab-the-capital-region-of-denmark/	Blog	21	0.27 %
/news/directed-presenting-at-tag-der-hydrology-2023-in-bochum/	/news/directed-presenting-at-tag-der-hydrology-2023-in-bochum/		16	0.20 %
/news/directed-at-ecca/	/news/directed-at-ecca/		15	0.19 %
/news/directed-presenting-at-egu-2023-in-vienna/	/news/directed-presenting-at-egu-2023-in-vienna/		15	0.19 %
The DIRECTED Project – Poster Presentation	/media-presentation/the-directed-project-poster-presentation/	Media / Presentations	9	0.11 %
DIRECTED AT ECCA	/news-posting/directed-at-ecca/	News	6	0.08 %
DIRECTED PROJECT LAUNCH	/news-posting/directed-project-launch/	News	6	0.08 %
DIRECTED AT TAG DER HYDROLOGY 2023 IN BOCHUM	/news-posting/directed-at-tag-der-hydrology-2023-in-bochum/	News	4	0.05 %
DIRECTED IS PRESENTING AT EGU 2023 IN VIENNA	/news-posting/directed-is-presenting-at-egu-2023-in-vienna/	News	4	0.05 %
/blog/the-directed-real-world-lab-at-the-capital-region-of-denmark-seeking-to-improve-future-governance-and-access-to-data-for-climate-emergencies/	/blog/the-directed-real-world-lab-at-the-capital-region-of-denmark-seeking-to-improve-future-governance-and-access-to-data-for-climate-emergencies/		3	0.04 %
Presentation at DAFF Forum in Budapest 11.10.2023 – Danube Region Real World Lab	/media-presentation/presentation-at-daff-forum-in-budapest-11-10-2023-danube-region-real-world-lab/	Media / Presentations	3	0.04 %
/productsolutions/	/productsolutions/		2	0.03 %
/blog/real-world-lab-at-the-capital-region-of-denmark-seeking-to-improve-future-governance-and-access-to-data-for-climate-emergencies/	/blog/real-world-lab-at-the-capital-region-of-denmark-seeking-to-improve-future-governance-and-access-to-data-for-climate-emergencies/		1	0.01 %
Sum			7,830	100.00 %

Figure 12: Most popular content on the project website.

Figure 13: Referrers from other websites to directedproject.eu.

Examples of Website pages of partners

SEI - <https://www.sei.org/projects/directed-climate-resilience/>

RIFS-Potsdam – <https://www.rifs-potsdam.de/en/research/disaster-resilience-extreme-climate-events-directed>

IIASA - <https://iiasa.ac.at/projects/directed>

PIK – <https://www.pik-potsdam.de/en/output/projects/all/958>

UCC/ MaREI - <https://www.marei.ie/project/directed/>

Genillard & Co - <https://www.genillard-co.com/our-projects/>

Branding and Templates – we have developed DIRECTED Branding and template reports, briefs, PowerPoint slide and posters and have used strong, but simple and clear branding.

Figure 14: Logo designs for the DIRECTED project.

Use of Videos

We developed an Introduction video for the Project aimed to inform people about the Project using the scientist, technologists and public authorities who talk about their excitement about the Project. <https://studio.youtube.com/video/Y3PuY3k1Q7o/edit>

We have also used video to track activities we are working on;

Extracts from Breaking the Silos, Serious Game : <https://youtu.be/EBrxTQmQnQM>

Recordings of webinars: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z6zIYe9HM-g>

Blogs

We have developed a range of blogs found here: <https://directedproject.eu/blog/> .

The blogs are posted on the website but also posted on our social media channels and posted as articles on LinkedIn.

Media Pack and Articles

Real World Lab informational leaflets can be found here:

<https://directedproject.eu/media/#press-information>

These leaflets will be used to accompany press releases.

Although we are in the early part of the Project media coverage has been gained: Reimagining Europe's Disaster Risk Reduction to cope with the climate crisis – by Janne Parviainen

Found here: <https://www.euractiv.com/section/climate-environment/opinion/reimagining-europes-disaster-risk-reduction-to-cope-with-the-climate-crisis/>

More articles with high profile media will be developed as we move forward in the Project.

Tool presentations

We have developed a product solutions section on our website to highlight most of the tools we are making interoperable. Find here: <https://directedproject.eu/product-solutions/>. Some tools have also be presented at conferences e.g. The Future Danube Model at the DAFF Conference, Budapest.

Conferences

We have attended a range of conferences. The details can be seen in D6.2 Communications and Dissemination Report Yr1. Conferences can be tracked in the Dissemination record as recorded on the Horizon Europe Portal.

Community of European Research and Innovation for Security (CERIS)

DIRECTED participated in two CERIS events in Brussels in June and December 2023. During the first event “Projects to Policy Seminar” we presented the DIRECTED project with our focus on the concept of interoperability to other Horizon Europe projects and EC representatives in the session for “Disaster Resilient Societies” (DRS). Many connections with Horizon Europe partner projects were made, common focus areas identified, and potential cross project synergies discussed.

We attended the Secure Societies ‘Projects to Policy Seminar’ jointly organised by DG Home and REA in Brussels in June 2023 where we have received guidance on the various communications, dissemination and exploitations tools available to us, as well as met our sister projects under the call of this grant. We have since been involved with discussions with our sister projects, and continued cooperation have been agreed.

DIRECTED was part of a fruitful exchange with fellow CERIS members on Panel 4 - Towards an all-society approach to disaster resilience: from research to policy recommendations - CERIS Disaster Resilient Societies: Annual event in December 2023. Video found here: <https://directedproject.eu/media/#videos-podcasts>

As a direct result from the CERIS meetings the DIRECTED project joined the CMINE Societal Resilience Cluster (SRC) and has been engaged with the group since October 2023.

Storyboard to assist content creation.

Other communications and dissemination tools developed for use by the project is the Directed Storyboard to help partners to create compelling stories and target specific audiences. Found [here](#).

Summary of social media coverage

Table 9: Summary Project Social Media Coverage for YR1 (excludes individual beneficiary engagement) found here.

Platform	Impression over 365 days	Engagement over 365 days Likes, comments & reposts
LinkedIn – DIRECTED Project Group	3776	77
LinkedIn – Oasis	22,332	334
X	7187	202
Instagram	Accounts reached not specified as not a professional account – we have now switched to a professional account	70
YouTube	213 views on you tube – does not include views from content placed elsewhere e.g. website	9.7 hours watching

It is clear from the figures that LinkedIn engages more with our material than the other platforms, which would be entirely logical as it is a place for disaster and climate adaptation professionals and therefore for 2024 we will focus on this platform for increasing our communications via social media. There have been many highly publicised changes on X that have decreased our reach, with more focus on celebrity over content. Nonetheless, our followers focus tends to be other European projects/ organisations linked to disaster management and climate change and therefore we will focus X communications on inter-project information communications. YouTube is used as storage for video that can be posted elsewhere. Instagram has gained a small following as would be expected for the type of content we produce. Finally, our Mastodon account has not taken off at all and therefore it would seem sensible to reduce content on here as it is not reaching our target audience.

Overall, including our website and social media content for Directed specific has reached in the region of 41,500 people. This figure should increase as our following grows over the next three years. These figures also do not include individual project partners figures.

Task 6.3. Identify current institutional capacity for integrated multi-hazard risk and Climate Change Adaptation (Month 2-9) (Lead: UCC)

Task 6.3 was led by UCC and resulted in Deliverable 6.3 Gaps and Needs Opportunities Assessment: knowledge transfer through training and education and puts forward a Knowledge Transfer Plan. As part of the task, a survey was completed within Directed consortium partners including the Real World Lab hosts (N=22), as well as a desktop review and key informant discussions with other projects and potential collaborators. The findings provided insights into partners' institutional knowledge, skills and attitudes around DRR/ CCA, existing and preferred training and educational activities, and collaboration opportunities with other projects, networks and platforms. Based on findings, the initial knowledge transfer mechanisms selected include the development of learning materials/ resources and delivery, in-person intensive learning activity (e.g. summer school), online learning programme (e.g. webinar or e-course), mentoring (e.g. students, interns) and cross-project collaboration (e.g. joint webinars). The Risk-Tandem Framework and the Data Fabric were identified as the key exploitable results to embed within knowledge transfer activities, through professional training, university teaching and e-Learning platforms. The target groups identified included: students/ researchers (e.g. university students, early career researchers); DRR/ CCA professionals, industry (e.g. insurance, private sector); and EU actors (e.g. other consortiums, professional bodies, networks/ forums). The Knowledge Transfer Plan is designed to complement the Capacity Development Strategy (D1.2), amplify the activities in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.1) and support the Business Development Plan (D6.5).

Task 6.4 Develop programmes to support integrated responses to multi-hazard risk and Climate Change Adaptation (Month 10-45) (Lead UCC) involves developing of learning and educational programmes scoping phase has begun picking up actions identified in the Knowledge Transfer Plan (D6.3). Currently, this involves organising a Knowledge Exchange Webinar Series to facilitate learning and exchange between other stakeholders and the RWLs (planned Spring 2024), 2) mapping exercise of educational and training collaborators and potential entry points including mentoring and supervision, 3) delivering guest lectures to build relationships with educators and 4) facilitating knowledge exchange with other EU projects (e.g. facilitating Danish RWL collaboration with City of Malmo via UNIC project workshop) . Once a core group of educators/trainers are identified a more intense co-design process (including workshops) will begin to ensure they are actively involved in the development and testing of learning resources for different target groups (Task 6.3) and identification of an e-Learning portal (D6.4) to collate and make available the resources for future use.

Task 6.6 Exploitation - Business planning with public and private sector for scaling outputs (Month 36-48) (Lead Oasis)

Not due. However, we are considering bringing the start date forward to month 30 to allow for longer IP consideration by partners, market research and competition analysis and to understand how the longer term exploitation of an open source platform and tools could work.

1.2.7 Work Package 7 – Project Management

1.2.7.1 Introduction

Work Package 7 is concerned with the management of the project to ensure efficient cooperation between all partners and successful completion of project objectives. Efforts in WP 7 are led by TU-Braunschweig with all project partners contributing to fulfil the tasks in this Work Package. The tasks in WP 7 run from the beginning of the project in month 1 until the end in month 48 with the stated goal to ensure exploitation and legacy beyond the projects completion. The Grant Agreement states that tasks in Work Package 7 include project coordination and administration (Task 7.1), project implementation, work planning, monitoring, reporting, and quality control (Task 7.2), as well as data management, exploitation, and impacts beyond the project's lifetime (Task 7.3). These tasks involve responsibilities such as ensuring timely submission of deliverables, financial and risk management, communication between consortium members and the EC, implementation of contractual changes, transparent overview of project activities, data management following FAIR principles, and maintenance of project outreach platforms and outputs.

Figure 15: Overview of the project governance structure.

Figure 15 depicts the projects governance structure created to ensure its successful operation. The DIRECTED consortium forms the project's foundation, with the general assembly as the central body of control and the grant and consortium agreements as formalizing documents. Management of the project relies on the agreed working plan and collaboration of partners set out in these documents. The management team consists of the project coordinator, the steering committee, and the management support team. To receive independent advice an external innovation advisory board and an ethics advisor are installed. For day to day operations and coordination in the project clear communication and regular exchange are paramount. Therefore, we make use of a number of project internal email lists, instant messaging via slack and video calls with Zoom. The bi-weekly "Jour Fixe" meetings have become the central point of exchange between all project partners.

1.2.7.2 Progress per task

Work Package 7 has closely collaborated and participated in the work of all other Work Packages in the project by providing the coordination and administration for the consortium. During this reporting period WP 7 was responsible for the formalization of the project structure through the signed Grant and Consortium agreements, the establishment of a working plan with risk management as well as a data management plan. The Table 10 below gives an overview of the progress made.

Table 10: Summary of deliverables, milestones, and tasks status in WP 7.

Deliverables, Milestones and Tasks	Status report
Deliverable D7.1 – Consortium Agreement including IPR, Grant Agreement signed Task 7.1	Status: Submitted The Consortium Agreement has been signed by all beneficiary and associated partners.
D7.2 – Project working plan with risk management and mitigation Task 7.3	Status: Submitted Document of the project working plan with risk management and mitigation was set-up and delivered. The document was updated with changes from the Grant Agreement and to risk management.
D7.3 – Data management plan Milestone 29 Task 7.3	Status: Submitted The DMP document was drafted and discussed in a PSC meeting reaching milestone 29. The DMP outlines the types of data to be collected, generated, and handled throughout the project. It is considered a living document to be updated over the course of the project, with a final version available at the end of the project. It addresses the scope of FAIR data management, allocation of resources, data security measures, and ethical aspects of the data generated through questionnaires and surveys.
D7.4 – Mid-term report, covering months 1-16 Milestone 30 Task 7.2	Status: Submitted A draft for the report has been created reaching milestone 30. The first mid-term report covering months 1-16 in the project has been delivered.
D7.5 – Mid-term report, covering months 17-32 Task 7.2	Status: on going Documentation for the second mid-term report covering months 17 - 32 in the project has begun

Task 7.1 Project Coordination and administration (Month 1-48) (lead: TUBS, contributors: WP leads: GFZ, OASIS, GECO, RIFS, SEI, UCC, 52N)

The DIRECTED project is underpinned by two fundamental agreements that establish its legal framework: the Consortium Agreement (CA) and the Grant Agreement. The CA outlines the participation, collaboration, and rights among the consortium partners, addressing project management, liability, access rights, and dispute resolution. This agreement was developed collaboratively, led by TUBS and involving project partners legal departments, and was signed before the project's initiation. The Grant Agreement describes DIRECTED's main objectives and tasks, providing a blueprint for project execution, including Work Package structure, management, and phases of inception, development, and evaluation. The Consortium Agreement for DIRECTED is based on version 1 of the DESCA template and sets the legal framework for cooperation between the project partners. Both agreements were signed by all project partners at the beginning of the project fulfilling deliverable 7.1.

Financial monitoring and reporting, handled primarily by TUBS, involves the distribution of pre-financing, regular financial reporting, and the monitoring of budget expenditure to avoid over- or underspending. Budget modifications, if necessary, are discussed within the PSC and decided upon in the General Assembly.

One **Amendment to the GA** was made within the first reporting period, when a name change of our partner IASS (Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies) to RIFS (Research Institute for Sustainability) and a full merger with the Helmholtz Centre Potsdam GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences occurred at the end of 2022. Included in this amendment was also a role change for our partner Christopher Genillard of G&C from CEO to the advisory board. This amendment has been completed at the time of reporting (AMD-101073978-7).

Task 7.2 Project implementation, work planning, monitoring, reporting and quality control (Month 1-48) (lead: TUBS, contributors: GFZ, OASIS, GECO, RIFS, SEI, UCC, 52N)

DIRECTED is structured around eight Work Packages, focusing on scientific and innovation tasks, knowledge transfer, project management, and ethics. A critical element is the establishment of Real World Labs in WP 1, which play a significant role in demonstrating and evaluating the tools and knowledge developed across the project. Ensuring effective communication and dissemination of project outcomes is also a priority, facilitated through workshops, trainings, and various communication strategies.

Project coordination is managed by TUBS, with Max Steinhausen as the coordinator. The project benefits from a Project Steering Committee (PSC) and a General Assembly, which are integral to the decision-making process and ensure cohesive progress across WPs. Additionally, an External Innovation Advisory Board (EIAB) is formed to provide expert advice on project outcomes, enhancing the project's impact in by innovating in the fields of Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA).

Project management emphasizes participatory design, continuous monitoring, and adaptive strategies to ensure compliance with planned activities. This includes the use of a [GANTT](#) chart for timing (See D7.2) and implementation monitoring, issue and risk logs for proactive management, and a structured process for deliverable development and reporting. Communication among project partners is facilitated through regular meetings, a cloud storage server for document exchange, and the project management platform ClickUp for task and progress tracking.

To foster seamless collaboration and information exchange among partners, DIRECTED incorporates bi-weekly web meetings, a dedicated cloud storage solution for document sharing, and regular updates on Work Package progress and Real World Lab activities. These mechanisms, alongside project meetings and workshops, support the co-development process and stakeholder engagement, ensuring the project's objectives are met effectively.

The international nature of our consortium with 18 project partners and our co-development approach make remote meetings and digital tools for collaborative work essential components for project management. Shortly after our in-person project kick-off meeting in Braunschweig we established a bi-weekly meeting open to all project partners the “Jour Fixe”. This remote meeting is primarily used to exchange information between the Work Packages and ensure that synergies can be exploited. Topical “deep-dive” talks are the second main point and the agenda. All participating partners have a chance to present their methodologies, data sets and models they contribute to the project. Deep-dive presentations are recorded and made available to all project partners for later reference. “Jour Fixe” meetings last for 1 hour and are usually joined by 15 – 25 team members.

Jour Fixe agenda:

1. Welcoming for new Project team members (farewells)
2. Deep dive presentations [10-20 minutes]
3. Updates from the WPs and RWLs [30-40 minutes]
4. Other business [10 minutes]

Cross Work Package meetings as described in each of the WP progress sections above are used for focused work and coordination in and between the WPs. These meetings are highly focused on specific tasks in the project and typically include multiple partners collaborating towards a joined deliverable or milestone.

The **Project Steering Committee** was established during the kick-off meeting in November 2022 in Braunschweig. The Project partners voted for one representative from each RWL and all WP leaders to constitute the PSC. Meetings in the PSC are held to discuss strategic decisions for project management and develop recommendations for the General Assembly of all project partners. The first PSC meeting was held on February 13th 2023 discussing the projects internal and external communication strategy such as the “Jour Fixe” meetings and conference attendance. The second PCS meeting was set to facilitate WP collaboration and communication and prepare strategic project decisions in prepare for the Cologne project meeting. Issues discussed included collaborations with EU partner projects, the EAIB candidates, the use of AI tools in the project and the internal deliverable review process. To coordinate the final writing of this midterm report an PSC meeting was held on March 12th 2024. Minutes from the PSC meetings are available for all consortium members on the ClickUp platform.

We maintain a **risk and issues log** for tracking the risks anticipated during project inception and for logging new unforeseen risks that arose during the projects' operation. A specially formatted spreadsheet accessible to all project partners and protected through version tracking was designed for that purpose. Risks are assessed by their potential severity on project success and by the likelihood of this risk occurring. All risks are assigned to an owner, usually the individual logging the risk or the lead of the WP the risk relates to. Strategies to manage and mitigate the risks and reduce their potential impact are devised by the consortium under moderation of the coordination team. The Risk and Issues log is regularly reviewed by individual project partners and the PSC.

Candidates for the **External Innovation Advisory Board (EIAB)** have been contacted with two members to be confirmed soon. First meetings with the board are scheduled to begin in May 2024. EIAB will be used as a sounding board for the potential of Innovations developed within the DIRECTED project. Seeking advise from the experts on the board will closely be linked to business and exploitation plan dues in month 30.

General Assemblies and project meetings

Braunschweig: In November 29th-30th 2022, the kick-off meeting was held in Braunschweig. This meeting was used to establish connections between all partners and across Work Packages. In the general assembly, the Project Steering Committee was constituted. The GA decided to hold all future annual project meetings in locations within the RWLs. This will enable all project partners to directly connect to local stakeholders and get first-hand information about the DRR and CCA challenges in the RWL.

Cologne: From September 18th-21st, 2023, the DIRECTED consortium partook in a **General Assembly (GA)** in Cologne and Bergheim. The focus of this meeting was on the set-up of the RWLs (Deliverable 1.1). During these four days, we were able to meet in-person with the members of the different teams, institutions, and companies that are all part of the project. It was an exciting few days visiting flooding sites, such as Erftverband, and areas partaking in nature-based solutions to mitigate flooding impacts. Each RWL also presented their current status, in terms of disasters the RWL faces and data needs, which was insightful information on the connection each presenter had to their given RWL. Also, during the GA, the consortium participated in a Serious Game, organized by WP 3 and WP 4. This game highlighted the need for data sharing and communication. Essentially, each team was given different maps and information, thus driving each team to advocate for different solutions, and not agree on a centralized one, because all had different information; thus, exemplifying the need for a centralized platform in disaster situations. Overall, the entire GA was a great learning experience, not only for the knowledge about the areas we gained, but also for the communications which were improved greatly by meeting face-to-face.

Rimini: We are currently in the preparation phase for our next General Assembly to be held in Rimini (Emilia-Romagna Region) from June 13th – 16th. The focus of this meeting will be on civil protection and the coordination of volunteers during disaster responds and recovery.

D 7.4 – Mid-term report, covering months 1-16

To coordinate the first mid-term report the coordination team prepared guidance documents for financial and technical reporting. These distributed via the directed mailing list to all consortium partners, presented during a “Jour Fixe” meeting and made available on the shared Nextcloud folder. All consortium partners submitted their financial reports on time. The only complication was a missing LEAR confirmation from the Erftverband due to a change in personal.

Task 7.3 Data management, exploitation and impacts beyond project lifetime (Month 1-48) (lead: TUBS, contributors: GFZ, OASIS, RIFS, SEI, UCC, 52N, GECO)

The Data Management Plan (DMP) (D7.3) for the DIRECTED project provides an overview of the types of data to be collected, generated, and handled throughout the project's duration and beyond. The DMP is understood as a living document that will be updated as significant changes arise during the project's operation, with a final version available at the end of the project. The initial version of the DMP aims to provide a general overview of data types collected and created by different project partners, aligning with the project objectives. With this initial version of the DMP we achieved Milestone 29. We specify the types of data generated in various Work Packages and the potential restrictions that may apply during the dissemination and exploitation of the data. At the heart of data management in DIRECTED is the FAIR Principle. The allocation of resources for various DMP-related activities. Additionally, the DMP addresses data security measures applicable to the project's data repositories and ethical aspects related to data generated through questionnaires and surveys. It summarizes the accessibility of the results of various tasks involved from all the WPs and includes a questionnaire circulated among the project partners to obtain information for the DMP as an annex. In terms of categorization, the data in the project can be classified into several categories,

including model data (input and output datasets), the Risk-Tandem Framework (setup and evaluation), the architecture of the DIRECTED Data Fabric (Data-Infrastructure), RWL surveys, interviews, and workshops, as well as policy recommendations.

1.2.8 Work Package 8 – Ethics

1.2.8.1 Introduction

Work Package 8 was implemented as a request from Horizon Europe to ensure ethical considerations, as advised by the EU, are reviewed and implemented to ensure good ethical practices of the DIRECTED Project. The DIRECTED Project has found it difficult to find suitably qualified people to implement the independent ethical advisor role, but we are now in a position to move forward with this Work Package as we have now been able to find a suitably qualified person. Therefore, as a result of this, all Work Package 8 deliverables have been delayed.

1.2.8.2 Progress per task

Table 11: Summary of deliverables, milestones, and tasks status in WP 8.

Deliverables, Milestones and Tasks	Status report
D8.1 – OEI - Requirement No. 1	<p>Ongoing/Delayed</p> <p>An independent Ethics Advisor with expertise in AI and ML to monitor the ethical concerns related to this project must be appointed. The applicant is invited to send the CV of the suggested Ethics Advisor and discuss their appointment with the Project Officer as soon as possible.</p> <p>A suitably qualified person has now been found and will begin work on D8.2 in April 2023. A CV has been viewed and accepted by the Project Officer and the CV has been submitted.</p>
D8.2 – OEI - Requirement No. 2	Planned/ Delayed – we intend to use the first report, as an inception report that outlines the ethical framework that the DIRECTED Project will follow and be assessed on.
D8.3 – OEI - Requirement No. 3	Not started
D8.4 – OEI - Requirement No. 4	Not started
D8.5 – OEI - Requirement No. 5	Not started

1.3 Impact

This section outlines our progress towards the planned impacts through highlighting some of the important impacts that have been achieved during the lifetime of the Project to this point. More detail of the Outcomes/ Outputs and Indicators and the main objectives can be found within the Grant Agreement.

It should be remembered that we are early in the Project, but despite this we have begun to show good indications that we are moving towards our longer term impacts at a good rate. Therefore, at this time, we are confident that there is no need to update our proposed impacts.

Table 12: DIRECTED Project Impacts.

Impacts Type	Impact	Outcomes/ Outputs	Linked Objectives	Evidence Indicators
Scientific impacts	The Tandem Process (SEI) has improved scientific workflows for stakeholder engagement and knowledge accumulation from stakeholders, by combining important tools to engage stakeholders in co-production and co-design. This has been achieved by using the Risk-Tandem Framework with stakeholder organisations in the Real World Lab.	Outcome 1 Output 1	SO3 SO4	Meeting minutes from RWL meetings D 3.1 Risk-Tandem Framework
Scientific impact	Improved capacity for the scientific community to couple data sets and models from multiple sources through the developed interoperability framework. A framework that outlines different pathways for interoperability has been developed that can be used long-term by scientists to increase interoperability of data and tools.	Outcome 4 Output 4	SO2	Report produced leading to Deliverable 2.1
Scientific impact	Improvements to the RIM2D model allowed faster GPU based hydraulic simulations used to in Denmark and Braunschweig, Erft	Outcome 4 Output 4	SO2	Model availability and feedback from RWL's
Societal Impact	In May 2023 major floods occurred in the Emilia-Romagna Regions, one of the Real World Labs, that resulted in loss of life, the displacement of thousands of people and 8.8 billion in damages. Between 16-18 May 2023, 350 million cubic metres of water, equivalent to six months' worth of rain, fell within 36 hours across Emilia-Romagna, one of	Outcome 4 Output 4 Indicator 4 Scale of contribution – Implemented in large-scale	SO7	Technical reports available

	<p>Italy's most important agricultural regions. The heavy rain led to the overflow of 23 rivers across the region, affecting 100 municipalities and triggering more than 400 landslides, which in turn damaged and closed off hundreds of roads. The floods were preceded by a drought that dried out the land, reducing its capacity to absorb water.</p> <p>The SaferPlaces Platform, was utilised by the Civil Protection of the Emilia-Romagna Region to generate flood water and depth maps to take crucial decisions after the disaster and support the assessment of the damages of the affected areas. The platform utilised satellite, climate data and AI-based models combined into a cloud computing environment to provide insights into areas prone to floods across the globe.</p> <p>Information on the flooded areas and the affected buildings conducted by local municipalities and data provided by the Emilia-Romagna Civil Protection were also integrated to fill the gaps and increase the accuracy of urban flooded areas when not captured by satellites. Maps portraying the extent of the flooded areas in the most affected municipalities, Faenza, Cesena, Forlì and Conselice, were generated with information on the depth and volume of the water.</p> <p>These maps provided crucial information for a preliminary Flood Damage Assessment to support the local and central authorities to estimate the damages as soon as possible. Specifically, the satellite-based water depth maps were used as input to assess the economic losses of affected buildings.</p> <p>Claudia Vezzani, Technical Manager of the Hydraulic Risk Area of the Civil Protection Agency of Emilia-Romagna Region, highlighted: "SaferPlaces technology and Earth observation data allow us to usefully support the disaster analyses and the computation of economic losses.'</p>	<p>regional flood event in Emilia-Romagna</p>		
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Societal impact	The Risk-Tandem Framework has been actively used in stakeholder engagement in the Danish, German and Italian RWLs successfully bringing together actors that traditionally do not exchange information in the field of DRR and CCA	Outcome 2 Output 2	SO3 SO4	Meeting minutes D 3.1 Risk-Tandem Framework
Societal impact	<p>Highlighting New Opportunities.</p> <p>The co-production process in RWLs opens new avenues for collaboration between stakeholders, researchers, and practitioners. This approach started in most of the Labs identifying innovative applicable solutions for DRM, DRR, and CCA, showcasing how transdisciplinary collaboration can lead to more effective and adaptable resilience strategies. For example, debriefing meetings where co-production tools were first utilized as a result of capacity development processes (WP 4) revealed that the co-production approach was considered effective in exploring complex information in a multi-stakeholder setting, compared to more traditional methods. Importance of Communication: RWL activities emphasized the importance of clear communication channels within RWLs and towards the external actors in DRR and CAA operation chains to reduce losses and effectively manage emergencies.</p>	Outcome 1 Output 1 Indicator 1	SO3 SO4	<p>Summary reports of meetings available</p> <p>Further evidence monitoring the impact and effectiveness of these approaches are planned in the coming months (WP 3 and 4).</p>
Societal impact	<p>The progress so far has revealed valuable insights that will shape the high level architecture of the Data Fabric. Impact has already been achieved through the meetings with the RWL leads raising awareness for already available solutions but also connecting stakeholders.</p> <p>The Dissemination of the results of DIRECTED has been started through sharing the ambitions of DIRECTED in conferences. Scientifically, the Data Fabric developed along with the rest of the DIRECTED consortium will contribute to open-source solutions to DRR and CCA strategies, and provide a framework for communication between diverse regions and climate change needs.</p>	Outcome 3 Output 3a	SO3 SO2 SO5	Meeting minutes

Societal impact	The (current) Danish version of the DamageCost model developed by DTU was adopted by the OS2 community, which is an open-source community for digital tools offered by and for public authorities in Denmark, completing the science to practice cycle.	Outcome 4 Output 4	SO2	Code and documentation available: https://www.os2.eu/os2-skadeso-konomi (in Danish)
Economic impact	<p>Increasing Awareness on Silos in Data Interoperability and Governance.</p> <p>WP 1 has spotlighted the fragmentation in data interoperability and governance practices. Through RWLs activities the project outlined the potential for cohesive data sharing and governance structures, emphasizing the need for a unified approach to data management across different sectors involved in disaster resilience.</p>	Outcome 6	SO4	Meeting reports and outputs

1.4 Publications

Publications are listed on the Funding and Tenders Portal. A more detailed list of all including non-scientific publications can be found in the Communications and Disseminations Report (D6.2)

1.5 Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results

Update for Dissemination

An update on plans for dissemination for Year 2 can be found in the deliverable D6.2 Communications and Dissemination Report Yr 1 at both project and beneficiary level. The report contains information of both a report of the previous years work and plans for Year 2 communication and dissemination. As we have now been working on the Year 2 Strategy for a few months, work has progressed and some of the predicted work within D6.2 has been completed. These include:

- e-Learning - A series of four webinars for internal stakeholders to share information within Real World Labs with a range of guest speakers has been planned and are currently being advertised with internal participants.
- An additional two papers are being worked on for the International Journal of DRR - focusing on topics around the co-creation, co-design, and co-validation of strategies and tools – bringing the total of papers planned for Yr 2 up from one to three papers.
- Two further blog posts have been completed as planned.

Update for Exploitation

As can be noted above under Task 6.3 Gaps and Opportunities report, work has been completed understanding some of the knowledge gaps and opportunities within stakeholders in the Project, to ensure stakeholders are better able to use the knowledge and product outputs of the Project more effectively.

Because of the strong stakeholder engagement programmes within DIRECTED outlined in WP 1, WP 3 and WP 4, foreground work is being conducted in understanding our stakeholders, their challenges and needs that are then being integrated into our Key Exploitable Results, in particular the Data Fabric and how that can solve some of the informational and organisational issues of cross organisational and cross boundary challenges that are being faced by stakeholders in our Real World Labs and developing the Risk-Tandem Framework into a tool that has use beyond the Project at hand, providing tools and methodologies that can better assist co-production and design of tools that will ultimately be used by those stakeholders for better Disaster and Climate Adaptation Management.

Therefore, as stakeholder engagement is a fundamental part of the Project – market readiness is likely to occur more quickly, with tools designed and already utilised in real world environments, with real world stakeholders – thus moving both of DIRECTED's main Key Exploitable Results into TRL 8 position by the end of the Project (see also).

As we are early in the DIRECTED Project, and the Data Fabric and the Risk-Tandem Framework are not in a finished form and thus not enabled to be shown to potential markets at this point in the Project, our D6.5 Exploitation Roadmap/ Business Plan has not yet begun and is due for completion in month 48. However, we are planning to bring the start date for this work forward to month 30 to enable longer IP consideration and arrangements by partners, market research and competition analysis and to understand how the longer term exploitation of Data Fabric and tools could work.

Our plans for engagement from M30 are as follows;

Intellectual Property – assess intellectual property arrangements required for future use of the tools developed (beyond the Project period)

Market Research – including demonstrations of tools to both RWL and external future potential users – targeting specific potential markets municipalities and local government, central government departments, first responder organisations, private sector e.g. relevant consultancies, insurance, recovery organisations.

Competitive Analysis – examining potential competitive tools and learning from them, where the tools we have developed sit within the target markets, as well as defining our USP within the existing market

Business Model Canvas Planning – defining the business models for each KER

SWOT Analysis

Market Targeting Analysis

Go-to-Market/ Exploitation Road Map development

Marketing Strategy + Investment material development

Exploitation/ Business Modelling e.g. income/ cost planning/ modelling – type of organisation who will host and assist long-term exploitation of the tools

Delivery Mechanism - (e.g. SaaS, external platform, licenses, subscription etc.)

P&L Modelling

Potential for Investment

Continuity of tools (remain in-house, development or exploitation by external partners)

Full use will be made of EU exploitation assistance where appropriate beginning in month 30 and we are currently in the process of understanding what is available to the Project.

Table 13: Progress on Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) levels.

Tool or model	TRL	Progress on innovations for interoperability	TRL
(a) SaferPLACES Digital Twin Solution for flood risk intelligence (GFZ, GECO)	7	[Web platform][Python code] Developing compliancy (API,REST) with RWLs input flood hazard/damage data (forecast and real-time). Output compliancy with Data Fabric and (b), (d), (e).	8
(b) RIMurban pluvial flood risk modelling and forecasting (GFZ)	6	[Numerical model] Added functionality for using additional input data sources, e.g. (c), and for merging model outputs (inundation maps) with data from other sources (remote sensing, VGI), and combining them with vulnerability models.	8
(c) Danube Model (PIK)	3	[Numerical Model] The Danube Model was reactivated with a new CaMa-Flood component, and the spatial discretization was streamlined from irregular subbasins to raster outputs with about four times higher resolution (~5 km with downscaling option to ~90 m).	5
(c) Seamless Forecasting Tool (PIK)	1	[Web platform] The fully implemented Danube Model shall be extended with seamless forecasting capability in a co-design mode with regional end users. For that purpose, a near real-time application has been tested with the Danube model so far.	2
(d) CLIMADA (ETH)	6	[Python code] (probabilistic risk assessment and adaptation option appraisal tool) Adding functionality for multi-criteria inputs and analyses.	8
(e) Damage Cost and Adaptation Model – DCAM (DTU)	6	[QGIS tool] Added input compliancy with hazard data from (a), (b), and (c). Output compliancy with Data Fabric. Alignment with damage cost functions used in CLIMADA. Within the reporting period, the original Danish version of this tool was further mainstreamed and operationalized via the OS2 community of public authorities in Denmark (TRL8). Explorative work and prototyping, implementing DamageCost damage cost functions into CLIMADA is being carried out at DTU for Central Copenhagen (TRL5-6). Collection of data from e.g. CLIMADA and SaferPlaces for making the model available at a European level is ongoing.	8
(f) Connectivity Hub (SEI)	1 taxonomy 6 Connectivity Hub	Development of an open-source taxonomy enabling external platforms to share qualitative data (e.g. lessons learned) seamlessly with the Hub (and other platforms/models potentially), to enhance 'search and discovery', and to maximise connections between the content.	
(g) Oasis-CAIMAN app (OASIS)*	6	Add flood hazard warnings (c), information on how to prepare for a disaster and links to, e.g. (a) and Data	8-9

		Fabric to ensure the wider exploitation of results.	
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2 Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous review

Nothing to report from previous reviews for reporting period 1.

3 Exploitation primarily in non-associated third countries

At present the entire project is working within the EU and therefore innovation work is being targeted here and at present there are no concrete plans for exploitation in non-associated third countries. However, this may change with progress in the business and exploitation plan.

4 Open Science

In relation to open science practices, numerous aspects can be highlighted. Many models and tools within the project are provided either as open-source and freely accessible (e.g. CLIMADA), or access can be granted upon request (e.g. RIM2D). Additionally, the codes for many of these tools (e.g. RIM2D, CLIMADA DamageCost Tool) are accessible on Git platforms, significantly enhancing their availability. Software developments of the components of the Data Fabric have also been made under open-source licences and have mostly been published freely accessible on GitHub. Technical models which are to be integrated into the Data Fabric are also mainly open source, such as the DTU cost damage model and CLIMADA, thus enabling the platform to be scalable and replicable. The open-source implementation therefore additionally supports further dissemination of the project infrastructure and practices to the broader EU.

Efforts have also been made to ensure that all publications related to this Work Package during the project are published as open-source. Some examples of these practices can be found in section 1.2.2.2. Further on, in WP 2, as part of the open-science and interoperability strategy, all partners will focus on ensuring that the results of this Work Package are produced in a manner that allows for consistent outcomes using the same data and/or methodologies.

All deliverables and project-related material intended for the public will be published on DIRECTED's website, and disseminated according to the communication plan (WP 6). First research papers (currently being drafted) will be published in open access journals to support open science practices. First results have already been shared and discussed on conferences and within bodies of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC).

5 Deviations from the project plan

5.1 Work Packages

5.1.1 Work Package 1

Below we outline and clarify the deviations from the Description of Action (DoA) encountered in some Real World Labs (RWLs) by the end of the reporting period. The inherent complexities of RWLs and the dynamic landscape of stakeholders, along with their evolving priorities, can naturally lead to unforeseen deviations or minor adjustments from the original plans, which are detailed below.

RWL 1: The Capital Region of Denmark

In our Real World Lab, after the intensive work carried out with stakeholders around the Roskilde Fjord until summer 2023, we have not engaged that actively with them during the period of October 2023 to January 2024. This relative slowdown of activities in the fall-winter period was decided to use the time planning activities for 2024. The strategy follows the availability and the wishes of stakeholders, going through a three step plan ranging from interviews with stakeholders over workshops to end up with a plan for a scenario play, enacting a potential disaster in the Roskilde Fjord area involving all relevant stakeholders in DRM and CC.

RWL 2: The Emilia-Romagna Region

As anticipated in the Real World Labs description and setup (D 1.1) after the first meeting an extreme flood occurred in the Region (in May 2023) stopping de facto for months all the activities of the lab as most participants were involved in emergency and post event recovery actions. This led to an initial delay of planned activities for the summer period, with the need to reschedule the second meeting (initially planned before summer) to the end of September. This contingency has already been addressed as the meeting took place in late September 2023 and the subsequent activities with stakeholders were effectively resumed in fall 2023.

RWL 3: Danube Region

In October 2023, we received indications from stakeholders from the research and insurance industry, who had actually shown interest in the project and a willingness to support us with information over the course of the year, that human resources were too scarce to regularly attend meetings and properly support the project. Despite intensive efforts in all key areas of civil and disaster protection, as well as the insurance industry, to encourage potential stakeholders to actively participate in the project, the support was insufficient to proceed with the Belgrade test site. As we were already able to acquire enough stakeholders from all key groups for the Vienna test site in Austria and the Zala region in Hungary to activate the RWL Danube Region, we decided to concentrate the main focus on these two test sites. However, for our RWL to be still well representative of the complexities faced in DRM, DRR and CCA in the Danube Region, we are not limiting ourselves to these two countries when acquiring further stakeholders.

Stakeholder recruitment in the Vienna test site on the part of civil protection agencies proved to be more challenging than anticipated. Although during meeting (video/phone calls) with stakeholders presenting the DIRECTED project or the Vienna test site, the necessity to pay more attention to climate change in order to better align disaster protection was emphasized, the perceived value of participating in the project as an information provider was generally

considered low. The reason for this could be related to the fact that the Vienna disaster protection system is perceived by stakeholders themselves as highly advanced and state of the art, already. Despite initial optimism, several attempts to win over crisis and disaster management as a stakeholder for our Vienna test site failed. However, as the disaster control offices of all Austrian provinces work closely together and we have the support of the disaster control of the province of Salzburg, this setback can be partially compensated for.

RWL 4: Rhine-Erft Region

The focus of RWL 4 is at the moment on the extreme event of flooding. As the region of the Rhine-Erft RWL was at least partially affected by the flood in July 2021, the extreme event of flooding is still very present in the minds of people and decision makers. Also, even after over two and a half years, the revision of the event is not yet finished, as shown by previous discussions with the stakeholders. That is why the focus of RWL 4 in DIRECTED has been on the extreme event of flooding so far. In the second half of the project, the focus will be shifted towards other extreme climatic events and CCA in the Rhine-Erft Region.

5.1.2 Work Package 2

There are no deviations from the planned schedule to report.

5.1.3 Work Package 3

There are no deviations from the planned schedule to report.

5.1.4 Work Package 4

Due to delays faced in setting up and operationalizing the RWLs, two milestones have been delayed. These include M19 (meeting minutes from scoping consultations for mapping capacity development needs) that were supposed to begin formally by month 9, but the first semi-structured interviews took place in month 15-16. Given that most of the RWLs were setting up their operations during 2023, needs for capacity development for co-production were low. However, WPs 3 and 4 have provided continuous support to RWLs through other engagements, including providing guidance for stakeholder identification and mapping (WP 3) which integrated Tandem guidance questions for enabling transdisciplinary spaces for collaboration (WP 4). Needs and opportunities were also scoped through knowledge co-production activities during the General Assembly in September 2023 in Cologne (evidence of which is now used to inform programming well beyond the context as described in D1.1). These (and the contributions to T2.1) therefore keep WP 4 on track to achieve its commitments as described under T4.2.

Linking to this delay, the first update report under M15 was submitted in August 2024 (annual report refining and updating the Tandem cycle based on emerging evidence, working toward M20 and D4.3). Although the application of the Tandem framework has begun within the Risk-Tandem process, empirical evidence that could support its refinement and further development have been sparse until Q4 of 2023 due to delays as described above. Now that the RWLs are fully operational, it is expected that the availability of data enabling the achievement of M20 will rapidly increase. In addition, researchers from WP 3 and WP 4 have co-authored a journal paper reviewing and assessing the barriers and enablers to facilitating co-production based on lessons learned, which will further compliment WP 4s efforts to achieve these objectives.

5.1.5 Work Package 5

Due to the different states of the RWL in their process to establish a multi actor platform, the requirement analysis is a bit delayed. However, this could be compensated through the assessment of components on a sub use-case level. With the addition of the use-cases from the Rhine-Erft and Emilia-Romagna RWLs, we will be able to identify and address potential challenges in the implementation process early-on.

5.1.6 Work Package 6

Deliverable D6.3 presents the Gaps and Opportunities Assessment to support knowledge transfer through training and education in the Directed Project. The report puts forward a Knowledge Transfer Plan to structure and guide the knowledge transfer activities in Directed in the DRR and CCA space. Work on this deliverable was delayed to allow more time for the setup of RWLs that are the key distributors and facilitators for knowledge transfer in the project. The findings from the Gaps and Opportunities Assessment The findings in this deliverable informed the Capacity Development Strategy (D1.2) and will connect with and amplify the activities in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.1) and Business Development Plan (D6.5). The delay on D6.3 has not impacted progress on these deliverables.

5.1.7 Work Package 7

Submission of the Project Working Plan (D7.2) was delayed on the EU portal due to a miscommunication in the WP 7 team. The work for D7.2 has been carried out on schedule and updated with changes to the GA and risk management and mitigation sections.

5.1.8 Work Package 8

Work Package 8 was implemented as a request from Horizon Europe in order to ensure ethical considerations are properly integrated and monitored throughout the project. The GA did unfortunately not allocate any time or budget to the Work Package. Finding a suitably qualified candidate via the ethics board of TUBS proved unsuccessfully and caused delays in all Work Package 8 deliverables. However, the project is now pleased to announce that two qualified advisors have been identified. The first candidate's CV has been presented to the Project Officer (D8.1). The second candidate will be presented at the beginning of April 2023. After choosing a candidate, work on the second deliverable (D8.2) will start in April 2023.

5.2 Use of resources

For all DIRECTED partners, the person months and personnel costs spent during the first reporting period are within the limits of the budgets allocated to them. The partner TUBS incurred some unforeseen costs in internally invoiced goods, which are duly reported. Furthermore, contrary to the announcement on page 30 of the DoA, the expenses for website creation and maintenance have been reported in 'Other goods, works and services' category instead of subcontracting, as per the regulations laid down by the European Commission.

The partner EV initiated set up of a new LEAR account for their organization due to internal changes within their organization. The confirmation of the account was not received before the reporting deadline of 31st March 2024 and thus, their costs have been left out of this reporting period.

As of January 2023, partner IASS (now renamed RIFS) officially merged with GFZ, which was officially communicated with the EC through the amendment AMD-101073978-7 launched on 15th June 2023. The PMs reported by IASS (RIFS) is therefore only for the period between 1st October and 31st December 2022. Their PMs thereafter are reported with GFZ.

A detailed description of the budget used per partner along with justifications wherever needed is provided in the UoR files complementary to this reporting. The following table provides an overview of the planned and executed person months per Work Package and partner in the first reporting period of the project.

Table 14: PMs planned vs. used in RP1 per partner and WP.

Partner	WPs							PMs used	Planned PMs in RP1	Progress made in RP1 (in %)
	WP 1	WP 2	WP 3	WP 4	WP 5	WP 6	WP 7			
1 TUBS	1.48	0.31	0.70	0.56	0.95	0.87	15.77	20.64	18.67	35.36
2 PIK	3.92	3.80			0.04	0.62		8.38	12.67	29.62
3 DTU	6.50	6.50	0.75	0.75	1.00	0.84		16.34	15.33	29.66
4 GECO	8.00	5.00		1.00	5.00	2.00		21.00	24.00	51.00
6 UCC	2.20		6.50	1.40		3.80	0.50	14.40	16.00	45.60
7 REGIONH	7.67					0.36		8.03	8.00	15.97

8 ARSTPC-ER	6.50					0.90		7.40	4.67	6.60
9 G&C	6.33	0.01	0.02	0.06		0.03		6.45	6.67	13.55
10 IIASA			1.60			0.10		1.70	8.67	24.30
11 EV	12.00							0.00	12	36.00
12 ZSRT	7.50	0.70	0.80			1.00		10.00	6.67	10.00
13 ARPAE	3.07					1.34		4.41	3.33	5.59
14 GFZ	1.60	7.90	5.30		0.50	0.30	0.30	15.90	29.33	72
IASS (RIFS)			0.10					0.10		
15 52N	0.75	1.94	0.01	0.01	11.19	0.19	0.03	14.12	13.33	25.88
16 ETH	2.00	6.00						8.00	8.00	
17 OASIS	0.78	0.05				7.93	0.83	9.58	9.67	
18 SEI		1.85	0.45	14.17		1.33	1.60	19.40	19.33	
PMs used	70.30	34.06	16.23	17.95	18.68	21.61	19,03			
Planned PMs	204	118	95	72	55	82	35			
PMs left	148.48	91.84	79.22	68.22	36.32	69.65	18.40			

5.2.1 Unforeseen subcontracting

None to report at this stage of the project.

5.2.2 Unforeseen use of in-kind contributions

None to report at this stage of the project.

6 Concluding remarks

The DIRECTED Project with a team 18 partner organisations has in the first 16 month of work laid the foundation for improving disaster resilience for societies adapting to a changing climate. During the establishment of our four Real World Labs we have built many valuable connections between the different actors on multiple governance levels and across sectors. This kind of collaboration is made possible by the co-development approach practised together with all project partners and stakeholders. The Risk-Tandem Framework is already showing its potential in overcoming silos in DRR and CCA research and practice. With the soon available design for the Data Fabric we will be able to integrate the interoperable use of data and models combined with innovative visualisation into our test beds in the RWLs. Further deepening and extending our network of stakeholders in the RWLs and beyond has high priority for the project. We are therefore specially looking forward to our next project meeting in the Italian RWL in June 2024.

Close collaboration with our partner projects in the CERIS community and via the CMINE Societal Resilience Cluster enables us to facilitate knowledge exchange across projects and European regions. These connections will also contribute to longer term lasting impacts especially on policy in DRR and CCA.

The DIRECTED Project is after the first 16 month of intensive work very well positioned to build impactful systems of interoperable data, models, communication and governance in our RWLs and beyond.

Annex 1

Table 15: Overview of project meetings (non-exhaustive list).

Meeting	Location	Date	Participants
WP-lead meeting	Online	11/11/22	all WP leads
Project kick-off	Brunswick	29/11/22	all
RWL 2 operative	Online	13/01/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE
RWL 2 operative	Online	20/01/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE
Risk-Tandem development	Online	20/01/23	SEI, UCC and RIFS
Scoping consultations with RWL 4 begin (M4.2).	Online	22/01/23	SEI, RWLs 1-4, UCC
Scoping consultations with RWL 2 begin (M4.2).	Online	23/01/23	SEI, RWLs 1-4, UCC
Steering Committee meeting 1	Online	14/02/23	Work Package leads, RWLs 1-4., TUBS
RWL 2 operative	Online	16/02/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE
Support for first RWL workshops	Online	17/02/23	SEI, UCC, RIFS, IIASA, TUBS, RWL 1, RWL 4
T2.1	Online	22/02/23	
WP 4/WP 5 coordination meeting	Online	03/03/23	52North, SEI
Interoperability coordination	Online	03/03/23	SEI, 52N
RWL 1 workshop debriefs and further support	Online	09/03/23	SEI, UCC, RIFS, RWLs 1-4
RWL 4	Online	13/03/23	EV, SEI, UCC, GECO, OasisHub, RIFS
Stakeholder engagement, RWL exchange	Online	13/03/23	EV, GECO, Oasis Hub, RIFS, SEI, UCC
Support for first RWL workshops	Online	13/03/23	SEI, UCC, RIFS, IIASA, TUBS, RWL 1, RWL 4
RWL 2 operative	Online	14/03/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE, Emilia-Romagna Region
RWL 2 1st Stakeholders Meeting	Bologna	21/03/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE, Emilia-Romagna Region, Stakeholders

Coordination of task 6.3.	Online	24/03/23	RIFS, GFZ, OASIS, SEI, TUBS, UCC
RWL 2 workshop debriefs and further support	Online	30/03/23	SEI, UCC, RIFS, RWLs 1-4
RWL 4	Online	21/04/23	EV, SEI, UCC
Support and exchange RWL	Online	21/04/23	EV, SEI, UCC
RWL 4 workshop debriefs and further support	Online	21/04/23	SEI, UCC, RIFS, RWLs 1-4
RWL 2 operative	Online	10/05/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE
Coordination of task 6.3.	Online	22/05/23	RIFS, GFZ, OASIS, SEI, TUBS, UCC
Preparation for the GA in Cologne	Online	07/06/23	UCC, SEI, RWL 4
Coordination of task 6.3.	Online	07/06/23	RIFS, GFZ, OASIS, SEI, TUBS, UCC
RWL 3 workshop debriefs and further support	Online	12/06/23	SEI, UCC, RIFS, RWLs 1-4
1st capacity development module	Online	15/06/23	RWLs 1-4
RWL 4	Online	06/07/23	EV, GECO, Oasis Hub
dissemination and case study	Online	06/07/23	EV, GECO, Oasis Hub
RWL 2 operative	Online	03/08/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE
RWL 4	Online	11/08/23	EV, Oasis Hub, SEI, TUB, 52°North
Support and needs RWL	Online	11/08/23	EV, Oasis Hub, SEI, TUB, 52°North
Scoping consultations and needs analysis for the Data Fabric (WP 5)	Online	11/08/23	RWLs 1, 3 and 4, 52North, SEI, DTU, GECO
WP 5 Rhine-Erft RWL	Online	11/08/23	52N, GECO, RWL Erftverband
T2.2	Online	12/08/23	
WP 5 Danube RWL	Online	17/08/23	52N, GECO, RWL Danube
Scoping consultations and needs analysis for the Data Fabric (WP 5)	Online	17/08/23	RWLs 1, 3 and 4, 52North, SEI, DTU, GECO
WP 5 Denmark RWL	Online	18/08/23	52N, GECO, DTU, RWL Denmark
Scoping consultations and needs analysis for the Data Fabric (WP 5)	Online	18/08/23	RWLs 1, 3 and 4, 52North, SEI, DTU, GECO

Coordination of task 6.3.	Online	24/08/23	RIFS, GFZ, OASIS, SEI, TUBS, UCC
Steering Committee meeting 2	Online	05/09/23	Work Package leads, RWLs 1-4., TUBS
RWL 2 operative	Online	12/09/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE
Preparation for the GA in Cologne	Online	13/09/23	UCC, SEI, RWL 4
General Assembly in Cologne	Online	18/09/23	All project partners
RWL 2 2nd Stakeholders Meeting	Ferrara	28/09/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE, Stakeholders
DAFF Event	Budapest	09/10/23	Christopher G. & present consortium
RWL 2 Debrief	Online	16/10/23	RWL 2, SEI, UCC
RWL 2 operative	Online	17/10/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE,
WP 3/WP 4 discussions to integrate Institutional Analysis Framework into Risk Tandem	Online	17/10/23	UCC; RIFS; SEI
T2.2	Online	15/11/23	
WP 5 modellers	Online	15/11/23	52N, GECO, GFZ, PIK, DTU, TUB, ETH, SEI
RWL 2 Webinar Data and Tools	Online	20/11/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE, Emilia-Romagna Region
Third stakeholder meeting	Bergheim	20/11/23	Representatives of EV, district of Euskirchen, district of Rhine-Erft, district of Rhein-Sieg, fire department Eftstadt, VdS Schadenverhütung GmbH, department of hydraulic engineering and water management University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU)
Insurance Stakeholder engagement	Vienna	26/11/23	Christopher G., representatives from Uniqa, Austrian Insurance Association and Generali
RWL 2 operative	Online	05/12/23	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE
RWL 3 Technical Meeting	Online	05/12/23	Stefano, Martin, Dominik
RWL 3 Lead & WP 4	Online	06/12/23	Janne, Christopher, Dominik
RWL 3 Testsite Update	Online	08/12/23	Levente, Dominik
WP 5 modellers	Online	08/12/23	52N, GECO, GFZ, PIK, DTU, TUB, ETH, SEI

Scoping consultations with RWL 1 begin (M4.2).	Online	13/12/23	SEI, RWLs 1-4, UCC
Scoping consultations with RWL 3 begin (M4.2).	Online	14/12/23	SEI, RWLs 1-4, UCC
RWL 3 & BMI Österreich	Online	04/01/24	Nieves Kautny, Dominik Hedderich
RWL 3 & EUADR	Online	15/01/24	Laszlo Balatonyi
RWL 2 operative	Online	16/01/24	RWL lead, GECO, ARPAE
T2.1	Online	16/01/24	
RWL 4	Online	22/01/24	EV, RIFS, Lena Hellfors
RWL 4	Online	22/01/24	EV, SEI, UCC, RIFS
master thesis Lena Hellfors in WP 3	Online	22/01/24	EV, RIFS
serious game/table top exercise RWL 4	Online	22/01/24	EV, RIFS, SEI, UCC
RWL 4	Online	08/02/24	EV, GFZ
RWL 4	Online	05/03/24	EV, GECO, Oasis Hub, RIFS, SEI, UCC
RWL 4	Online	06/03/24	EV, 52°North, TUB, Stakeholder
Steering Committee meeting 3	Online	12/03/24	Work Package leads, RWLs 1-4., TUBS
WP 3/WP 4 coordination meeting	Online	Every Monday	SEI, UCC, RIFS, IIASA, TUBS, OASIS
DIRECTED Jour-Fixe	Online	Every other Thursday	All project partners and RWLs
WP 5 internal meeting	Online	Frequent (slack)	52N, GECO,

Partners

